

RERAM

research to innovation in
resource efficiency

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www.reram.eu

Transnational Trainings of Experts

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4 – UNFU Ukrainian National Forestry University

Main author

Roman Shchupakivskyy, UNFU

Approved by

Uwe Kies, IWH (coordinator)

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Ukrainian National Forestry University
Gen. Tchuprynka str., 103, 79057, Lviv, Ukraine
fon: +38 032 238 45 04
<http://tvd.org.ua>

Wald-Zentrum

Internationales Institut für Wald und Holz NRW e.V.
Hafenweg 24a, 48155 Münster, Germany
fon +49 251 674 3240, fax +49 251 674 32421
www.wald-zentrum.de

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1. WP2 Objectives

This deliverable D2.1 is a summary activity report of the transnational trainings of experts of the RERAM project and contains an overview of the progress during the period M01-M06, 1st June 2014 to 30th November 2014 in relation to two main tasks of Work Package 2 (WP2). The main purpose of the WP2 is to carry out an overall sectoral and enterprise-level analysis of the forest-wood-chain using existing sources of information.

- Task 2.1: Transnational training sessions and feedback for regional expert focus groups; and
- Task 2.2: Survey 'Self-Assessment of wood-working enterprises on saving potentials for wood raw material use and energy consumption'.

T2.1 main objectives are to conduct:

1. Transnational training sessions for regional experts (organized by UNFU and HCS);
2. Adaptation and adjustments of the survey guidelines to specificities in the ENP eastern countries;
3. Final workshop on the lessons learned (feedback workshop including expert focus groups and representatives of enterprises).

Therefore a series of training and feedback meetings of expert focus groups are conducted to enhance their methodological and practical knowledge in regional baseline analysis of the forest-based sector.

T2.2 main objective is to develop a simplified, easily applicable method to assess wood resources efficiency on the company level. It should include a questionnaire and a calculation tool, which can be applied by company owners themselves to evaluate their performance of material and energy use in economic terms. The questionnaire survey will be performed with groups of selected enterprises in several participating regions, which serves as a pre-check for the benchmarking exercise in WP3.

2. Progress and Achievements

During the period the RERAM project has conducted three meetings corresponding to T2.1 and T2.2: (1) Kickoff meeting in Münster, Germany, 14-15 July 2014, (2) Start of WP2 meeting, 16-17 July 2014 in Münster, (3) Training Week in Lviv, Ukraine, 13-17 of October 2014. The following chapters document the progress of work during these meetings.

2.1 Kickoff meeting in Münster, Germany, 14-15 July 2014

Day 2 – Introduction to WP2, by Prof. Orest Kiyko

The presentation considered the main goals and objectives of separate work packages and the RERAM project as a whole and their implementation to achieve the set objectives. The introduction was dedicated to the start of the Work Package 2 ‘Regional Baselines in Resource Efficiency’ and considered the objectives and tasks of WP2, the outputs and deliverables, expectations from the consortium members. The main agreed terms and deadlines of WP2 specifically were:

- All countries-participants of RERAM project have specified all features for their surveys and self-assessment fulfillment until the end of M4 (September, 2014).
- Common methodology finally agreed until the end of M5 (October, 2014).
- All countries-participants of RERAM project have completed their self-assessment until the end of M7 (December, 2014).
- All countries-participants of RERAM project have completed their surveys until the end of M12 (May, 2015).
- Self-assessment report completed until the end of M9 (February, 2015) and Baseline report completed until the end of M15 (August, 2015).

→ Annex 4.1.2: WP2 Regional Baselines - Introduction

2.2 Start of WP2 Meeting, Münster, Germany, 16-17 July 2014

Day 3 - Excursions

The start of WP2 was implemented through excursions to leading woodworking enterprises and competence centres in the NRW region.

- Excursion point 1: “EGGER Holzwerkstoffe Brilon” (www.egger.com). Guided tour of a large wood processing industry cluster integrating sawmilling, wood panel production and bioenergy plant. Short review of the main technological operations and stages, modern technologies, innovation, resource efficiency and energy saving systems in the enterprise. Brief excursion into the history and formation of the company, the priority ways of its development and future strategy.

- Excursion point 2: **I.D.E.E. (Information and Demonstration Centre for Renewable Energies, www.idee-nrw.de)**. A brief overview of the centre, its activities and priorities. Tour of the exhibition hall of modern energy saving systems from the leading regional producers.
- Guest presentation by “**Effizienz-Agentur NRW**”, **Mr. Ekkehard Wiechel (EA-NRW, www.ressourceneffizienz.de)**, on the **PIUS-Efficiency-Check** for wood industries in NRW. Discussion on approaches and basic principles for assessing the state of energy and resource efficiency in wood processing companies.
- Excursion point 3: Guided tour of a small processing sawmilling plant – «**Baust Holzbetrieb GmbH**» (www.baustholz.de). Acquaintance with the realities of becoming and of the company, an overview of the production process and waste management.

Day 4 – WP2 working group meeting

Two presentations devoted to T2.1 and T2.2 were given.

1. The main objectives and methodology for the global survey of forest-based sector in ENP countries and the basic characteristics of the analysis were presented. A Ukrainian example of global survey was provided. A number of questions and nuances of the analysis were discussed and approved, as follows:

- For RERAM project will be used UNFU definition of the forest sector.
- National analyses will carry out Ukraine, Moldova and Georgia.
- Regional analysis will carry out only Ukraine as the largest ENP country. Moldova and Georgia will identify some features for the regional forest sectors development.
- EU countries (AT, DE, PL) can determine main parameters of the national and regional forest sectors in order to compare them respectively with ENP ones.
- UNFU methodology will be used as the basic set of parameters.
- 5-year period (from 2008 to 2012) will be used for the global analyses.

2. The main objectives of the self-assessment and its methodology were presented (approach; implementation; expected outcomes). The developed questionnaire, its structure and ways of use were presented. The main indicators for raw materials and resource efficiency use to be implemented in the calculation tool were discussed. The consortium agreed on the following points in regard to self-assessment of wood-working enterprises:

- The self assessment of wood-working enterprises will be carried out in all ENP countries, in Austria and in selected cases in Poland.
- Number of completed questionnaires from each target region must be at least 10-15.
- Each of the participating countries can add a few supplementary questions to the survey, if necessary.
- The results of the previous self-assessment of identified wood-working enterprises in Ukraine must be received until October, 2014.

The following next steps in regard to global survey were agreed.

- All countries should send suggestions for improvement questionnaire to the responsible person for WP2 until August, 31 (2014) in the event of the necessity.
- Send output version of questionnaire to the project members – until the 15th of September (2014).
- Send questionnaires to identified enterprises – deadline October, 30.
- Receive filled up questionnaires from the partner countries of the RERAM project until the 30th of November.
- Processing questionnaires (with the support and guidance of the responsible party) until December, 20.

→ **Annex 4.1.1: Start of WP2 Meeting / Transnational Training - Minutes**

→ **Annex 4.1.3: WP2 Regional Baselines - Training T2.1 Global Survey**

→ **Annex 4.1.4: WP2 Regional Baselines - Training T2.2 Questionnaire Survey**

2.3 Training of experts in Lviv, Ukraine, 13-17 October 2014

Day 1 – First training session

The train-the-trainers programme in resource and energy efficiency management was hosted in Lviv, Ukraine by the Ukrainian National Forestry University (UNFU) and FORZA NGO. The training programme was provided by the Austrian Wood Cluster Styria (HCS) in collaboration with two experienced trainers Thomas Dielacher and Christian Angerbauer. A group of 15 wood industry experts from EU and ENP countries gathered in Lviv for the one-week hands-on training programme. In practical training sessions and company visits, the trainers introduced the trainees to effective methods for efficiency checks of enterprises.

During the first day, the project, its participants, the purpose, objectives and main expectations of the Training Week were introduced by the coordinator and the WP2 leader.

The two trainers started with a short overview of the training program and its implementation. The training modules comprise theoretical introductions and interactive exercises on i) Cleaner Production and Resource Efficiency, ii) Material flow analysis, iii) Water Management and Waste Management, iv) Tools and Efficiency Guidelines. Core subjects were the issues relating to connections between CP and ECO-efficiency, principles of input/output analysis, strategies for CP-options, etc.

Group sessions with active involvement of the participants applied the concepts studied during the day. The group discussions focused on explanations of false steps in the depicted real case examples of CP-options. The key take-home-messages of group assignments were the group's conclusions presented by the group leaders.

→ **Annex 4.2.1: Training Week Lviv - Minutes**

→ **Annex 4.2.2: Impressions of the Lviv training workshops**

Day 2 – Excursions

During the second working day of the project participants carried out three study tours to woodworking enterprises located in the Lviv region.

Excursion point 1 was study tour of wood processing industry enterprise (window producer) **FAKRO-LVIV** (www.fakro.com.ua). Within the guided tour by the director and chief engineer participants familiarized with main production areas of the enterprise and learned various aspects of the progress of technological processing.

Excursion point 2 was a study tour of wood processing industry enterprise **BUK-Holding** (www.bukholding.com.ua/index.php/en), which provides the following products from wood: windows, doors, stairs and staircases, balusters, barriers, other small wooden items for interior design, etc. The excursion through the company area and meetings with engineering staff highlighted issues of energy and resource conservation, facilitated by the trainers.

Excursion point 3 was the woodworking company **YurVit** (<http://yurvit.com.ua/uk/>), which produces furniture mainly from solid wood. Special attention was paid to the factors of technological process and used equipment. As a result of the tour a joint discussion with the director was held about the features of technological process at the enterprise, problems and difficulties of production, etc.

Project participants also visited the **PROFESSIONAL SCHOOL # 17** (81070, Ukraine, Lviv oblast, Yavorivsky district, v. Ivano-Frankove, Market square 13) where they had the opportunity to familiarize themselves with the craft works of local graduates. During the meeting with the professional school teachers the group discussed also the prospects for the woodworking and forestry vocational education in Ukraine.

→ Annex 4.2.3: Impressions of Excursions and Reality Check

Day 3 – Second training session

The WS2 day focussed on poster presentations and practical group tasks devoted to interactive inputs on Material Flow Analysis (MFA). As a result of working on the tasks, each group expressed their vision for the Strategies for CP-options, MFA and possible approaches to solving this problem. Trainers made a detailed analysis of accepted approaches, basic principles, errors and obtained results due to the exercises in working groups.

Besides, participants learned basic approaches of Initial Audit/Reality Check such as: main definitions and goals of an environmental audit, objectives for the initial RE audit, main requirements for a qualified auditor, interview steps and question techniques, main requirements for audit outcomes.

As one side event, a press conference was held by selected consortium participants to inform the wood industry newspapers and local press about the training week. Furthermore,

separate bilateral meetings of wood industry professionals, representatives and researchers from Ukraine, Georgia and EU member states were organized.

→ **Annex 4.2.2: Impressions of the Lviv training workshops**

→ **Annex 4.2.4: Impressions of side events**

Day 4 – Reality Check Day

The excursion's purpose was to perform a full-day Reality Check of the furniture enterprise **Mebly-Styl** (<http://www.meblistil.com/>). The owner and director of the company Mr. Volodymyr Turchyn introduced the group to the history of the company, state and prospects of its development. Then the group had a walk through all processing units of the plant, where manifold questions and aspects were discussed with the owner and entrepreneur/technical staff. The processing departments comprised: main production floors and raw-material storage area, drying department, department of cutting sawn timber into the workpieces, workshop for furniture frames manufacturing, department of foam rubber cutting, frame and house assembly of furniture, workshop of preparation and cutting upholstery tissues, testing laboratory, workshop for the furniture production from chipboard, boiler house, aspiration and pneumatic systems, compressor station, electro panel and transformer substation, station of water supply.

During the reality check the two Austrian expert trainers performed a complete first assessment of weaknesses relating to flows of energy and material resources in the enterprise. At the end of the initial check day, a round table discussion with the enterprise owner was held, where the experts indicated their identified main weak points, and where all training participants had the opportunity to share notes and comments, as well as ideas for the implementation of energy and resource improvement approaches.

→ **Annex 4.2.3: Impressions of Excursions and Reality Check**

Day 5 – Third training session

The WS3 day included presentations and interactive sessions about Water Management and Waste Management. The trainers explained in detail the principles of work organization during a reality check activity of an enterprise. A practical group exercise on the topic of MFA was carried out. Each group discussed their chosen approaches summarizing the results of lessons. Based on their experience gained in the training, the participants analysed the state of resource and energy efficiency of the Mebly-Styl enterprise.

The following next steps in the RERAM project and important term points in regard to the further self-assessment of wood-working enterprises were agreed:

- All questionnaires must be received by end of November 2014;
- All information must be strictly confidential and can only be given out to team members within the project.
- Proposed and agreed date and place for the second training week is the 9-13 February 2014 in Vienna-Graz (5 days) with 15-20 participants.

The Austrian trainers of the HCS Holzcluster Steiermark GmbH, C. Angerbauer and T. Dielacher, provided all workshop participants with a set of three Training Manuals, which document all training workshop topics and contents and shall be used as reference material during the upcoming enterprise checks in the ENP target regions.

- **Annex 4.2.1: Training Week Lviv - Minutes**
- **Annex 4.3.1: Training Manual 1 – Cleaner Production**
- **Annex 4.3.2: Training Manual 2 – Material Flow Analysis**
- **Annex 4.3.3: Training Manual 3 – Waste Management**

3. WP2 Timeline including Next Steps

DATE	EVENT	LOCATION	HOST/ RESPONSIBLE
16-17 JULY 2014	Start of WP2 Meeting	Münster, Germany	IIWH, UNFU
13-17 OCT 2014	1 st Training Week	Lviv, Ukraine	UNFU, FORZA, HCS
09-13 FEB 2015	2 nd Training Week	Graz/Zeltweg, Austria	HCS
MAR 2015	WP2 Interim report D2.2	-	UNFU
MAY/JUNE 2015 (TENTATIVE)	Training and Enterprise Check	Tbilisi, Georgia	RECC, AUG, HCS
OCT 2015	WP2 final report D2.3	-	UNFU

4. Annex

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¹ by UNFU, O. Kiyko and R. Shchupakivskyy

² Minutes by UNFU, photo credits by FORZA NGO and UNFU

³ by HCS, Ch. Angerbauer and T. Dielacher

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Start of WP2 Meeting / Transnational Training Minutes

Date

16 - 17 July 2014

Venue

**TREFF HOTEL Münster
Stubengasse 33, 48143 Münster, Germany**

prepared by

**Orest Kiyko (UNFU)
Roman Shchupakivskyy (UNFU)**

UNFU - Ukrainian National Forestry University
Department of Technology of Furniture and Wood Products
11, Zaliznjaka str., Lviv , Ukraine, 79057
<http://tvd.org.ua>

List of participants

Nr	Beneficiary	Attendant (First name, surname)
01	IIWH, Germany	Uwe Kies
02	IIWH, Germany	Susanne Bergmann
03	IIWH, Germany	Monika Papenberg
04	HCS, Austria	Roland Oberwimmer
05	ITD, Poland	Magdalena Herbeć
06	UNFU, Ukraine	Orest Kiyko
07	UNFU, Ukraine	Roman Shchupakivskyy
08	FORZA, Ukraine	Lesya Loyko
09	FORZA, Ukraine	Natalia Voloshyn
10	AITT, Moldova	Roman Chirca
11	AITT, Moldova	Vadim Iatchevici
12	AITT, Moldova	Oleg Pertrache
13	RECC, Georgia	Sophiko Akhobadze
14	AUG, Georgia	Teimuraz Kandelaki
15	AUG, Georgia	Nana Goginashvili

Wednesday, 16.07.2014

red = reference to presentations (numbered) or documents on CD-Rom or shared webspace.

Time	Activity, Presentation
8:00	Start of Excursion day to Sauerland region Meeting lobby Treff-Hotel; Bus drive to Brilon
09:30	Excursion point 1: EGGER Holzwerkstoffe Brilon Guided tour of a large wood processing industry cluster integrating sawmilling, wood panel production and bioenergy plant www.egger.com
12:30	Bus drive from Brilon to Olsberg
13:00	Arrival & Lunch at I.D.E.E. Information and Demonstration for Renewable Energies Centre Short introduction to the Centre, www.ideo-nrw.de
14:00	Guest presentation: PIUS-Efficiency-Check for Wood Industries Guest: Effizienz Agentur NRW, Mr. Ekkehard Wichel, www.efanrw.de The Effizienz-Agentur NRW supports SMEs in Nordrhein-Westfalen in the planning and implementation of their individual projects in cleaner production (PIUS). It was founded in 1998 as an initiative of the NRW Ministry for the Environment. The objective is the improvement of production resource efficiency, from which both companies and the environment equally benefit. → EFA_PIUS-Check_Wichel_RERAM-Kick-off_2014-07-16.pdf Moderator: Prof. Dr. Orest Kiyko, UNFU - Relevance / Benefits for WP2
15:00	Bus drive from Olsberg to Eslohe
15:30	Excursion point 2: Baust Guided tour of a small processing sawmilling plant; www.baust.de
17:00	Bus drive back to Münster
18:30	Arrival at hotel

Thursday, 17.07.2014

red = reference to presentations (numbered) or documents on CD-Rom or shared webspace.

Time	Activity, Presentation
9:00	<p>WP2 - Regional Baselines in Resource and Raw Material Efficiency:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Global survey of forest-based sector in ENP countries <p>Prof. Dr. Orest Kiyko, UNFU:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Overview 01_WP2_T21_Global_Survey_Kiyko.pdf 2. Global survey approach.pdf 3. Ukrainian example of global survey.pdf <p>Questions/Answers (Q/A) as follows were discussed in detail.</p> <p>Q/A: Which countries of the RERAM project should carry out regional and national surveys? All ENP countries (Ukraine, Moldova and Georgia) should carry out such surveys. In particular Ukraine will carry out regional and national survey as the largest ENP country. Moldova and Georgia will carry out national surveys and maybe additionally they will determine some regional features. NRW, Poland and Austria will carry out some partial analyses for comparison with ENP countries.</p> <p>Q/A: Will we use such titles as “woodworking” or “forestry sector” in our project? We can use a lot of different titles in RERAM project but it is suggested to use as common title ‘forest-based sector’ as common international terminology (EC, FAO, etc.)</p> <p>Q/A: What should we do in the event when some indexes are absent in our national data base? You can estimate indexes based on some similar indexes or assumptions and clearly mark these as “estimated indexes”; you can use experts’ opinions and estimation; you can miss this field writing “data is not available”.</p> <p>Q/A: Explain the additional necessity of determining the indexes turnover, number of enterprises and number of employees. We can consider these parameters which you mentioned as the main parameters since thanks to them we will be able to identify national and regional forest sectors, to determine “average” enterprises of these sectors, to determine some main trends and tendencies of the forest sector development.</p>

	<p>Comments from consortium members:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Uwe Kies: The global analyses should give a good overview on the current situation of the forest sector, based on key statistics/indexes and available literature/reports. The results should also give an outlook on major trends and the future of the forest-based sector development, based on available information (qualitative, in case quantitative info is lacking). This outlook is especially important for the target group of decision-makers in industry, authorities and policy, and should lead to the conclusion of recommendations – which can then be used as a basis for WP4 R2I dialogues (roundtables). - T. Kandelaki: The WP2 baseline study has to take account of the ongoing (policy) reforms in the forest-based sector. <p>The consortium agreed on the following points in regard to global survey.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - For RERAM project we will use UNFU definition of the forest sector. - National analyses will carry out Ukraine, Moldova and Georgia. - Regional analysis will carry out only Ukraine as the largest ENP country. Moldova and Georgia will identify some features for the regional forest sectors development. - EU countries (AT, DE, PL) can determine main parameters of the national and regional forest sectors in order to compare them respectively with ENP ones. - We will use as the basic set of parameters according to UNFU methodology. - We will use 5-year period (from 2008 to 2012) for the global analyses. - All countries-participants of RERAM project can add some supplementary points in their global surveys in the event of the necessity. <p>The following next steps in regard to global survey were agreed.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - All countries-participants of RERAM project have specified all features for their surveys fulfilment until the end of M4 (September, 2014). - All countries-participants of RERAM project have completed their national surveys until the end of M6 (November, 2014). - All countries-participants of RERAM project have completed their regional surveys until the end of M8 (January, 2015). - An on-line web-conference has been conducted for final adjustment and comparison among EU and ENP until the end of M10 (March, 2015). - All countries-participants of RERAM project have completed their surveys until the end of M12 (May, 2015). - Baseline analyses and report completed until end of M15 (August, 2015).
10:45	Coffee break

11:00	<p>WP2 - Regional Baselines in Resource and Raw Material Efficiency:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Questionnaire survey “Company self-assessment” Roman Shchupakivskyy, UNFU <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Overview - 02_WP2_T22_Questionnaire_Survey_Shchupakivskyy.pdf 2. Questionnaire - Questionnaire v.1.10.pdf <p>Q/A: Which countries of the RERAM project should conduct surveys at the woodworking enterprises?</p> <p>We suggest to carry out the survey in ENP countries (Ukraine, Moldova and Georgia) as well as in Austria, and optionally at 2-3 enterprises in Poland.</p> <p>Q/A: What is the recommended number of enterprises to be interviewed for each country at the regional level?</p> <p>In order to use internal and external benchmarking approach it is supposed to get at least 10-15 fully-developed questionnaires for each country.</p> <p>Q/A: What are the basic requirements for companies that will be offered for the survey?</p> <p>We can distinguish few basic requirements for such enterprises: it’s should be representatives of the regional forest sector with different number of employees, volume and degree of wood products processing, and they should be dealing with solid wood. The list of target companies per region needs to be communicated to the WP2 Leader in order to get a good picture which industries are covered.</p> <p>Q/A: Will it be possible to do only partial filling of the questionnaire?</p> <p>We recommend fill out the form to the fullest extent especially for companies that intend to make a real-check of the energy and resource efficiency.</p> <p>In the discussion the consortium agreed on the following points in regard to self-assessment of wood-working enterprises:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - self assessment of wood-working enterprises will carry out all ENP countries, Austria and quite local Poland; - number of completed questionnaires from each target region must be at least of 10-15; - each of the participating countries can make some supplementary questions to the survey, if necessary; - the results of the previous self-assessment of identified wood-working enterprises in Ukraine must be received till October, 2014; - results of completed applications will be processed directly by UNFU.
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	<p>The following next steps in regard to global survey were agreed.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Leaders of WP2 (UNFU) and WP3 (HCS) communicate and agree on the list of parameters/indices to be collected and analysed during the survey. - all countries should send suggestions for improvement questionnaire to the responsible person for WP2 until August, 31 (2014) in the event of the necessity; - send output version of questionnaire to the project members – till the 15th of September (2014); - send questionnaires to identified enterprises – deadline October, 30. - receive filled up questionnaires from the partner countries of the RERAM project till the 30th of November; - processing questionnaires (with the support and guidance of the responsible party) till December, 20; - results and survey report – March 2015.
12:30	End of meeting; Individual departure

For the Minutes:

Orest Kiyko

Roman Shchupakivskyy

For the Coordinator:

Uwe Kies

WP2 - Regional Baselines in Resource and Raw Material Efficiency Introduction

RERAM

BRIDGING GAPS BETWEEN R2I IN RESOURCE EFFICIENCY AND RAW MATERIALS

FP7-INCO Coordination Project 2014-2015

Kick-Off Meeting – Munster (14-17.07.2014)

Prof. Orest Kiyko

Ukrainian National Forestry University (UNFU)

Head of the furniture and wooden articles
technology Department

Contents

- **1. Common information.**
- **2. Objectives and tasks.**
- **3. Outputs and deliverables.**
- **4. What do we expect from project and the consortium members?**
- **5. Discussion and conclusions.**

RERAM's IDEA

ENP countries and economical problems

Importance of the forest sectors development in the ENP countries

Two options of the forest sector development: intensive or extensive development

EU countries have some experience and some knowledge in regard to intensive development of their forest sectors

2020 strategy and importance of the response on the main challenges

RERAM responds to the societal challenge of "CLIMATE CHANGE, RESOURCE EFFICIENCY AND RAW MATERIALS"

Do we have some relation between two definition?

1. Intensive usage of wood resources

2. Societal challenge "CLIMATE CHANGE"

Forest sector offers a simple way to reduce the CO₂ emissions that are the main cause of Climate Change, through:

- the carbon sink effect of the forests;
- the carbon storage effect of wood products;
- substitution for carbon-intensive materials.

RERAM's IDEA

**It is very difficult to drink water from a sieve.
We should at least try to close those holes or maybe to decrease their number.**

Ukrainian National Forestry University. Department of the furniture and wooden articles technology

Work package number ⁵³	WP2	Type of activity ⁵⁴	OTHER
Work package title	Regional Baselines in Resource and Raw Material Efficiency		
Start month	1		
End month	17		
Lead beneficiary number ⁵⁵	5		

WP leader UNFU, co-leader IIWH

Person-Months per Participant		
Participant number ¹⁰	Participant short name ¹¹	Person-months per participant
1	IIWH	3.00
2	HCS	1.00
4	ITD	2.00
5	UNFU	8.00
6	FORZA	3.00
7	WPFC	2.00
8	AITT	4.00
9	RECC	2.00
10	AUG	6.00
	Total	31.00

Ukrainian National Forestry University. Department of the furniture and wooden articles technology

MAIN IDEA of the WP2

WP2 starts off with a national and regional-level baseline assessment of existing useable information on forest resources, wood raw materials, related industries and actors in the R2I chain (WT2.1). The second step (WT2.2) comprises a broader questionnaire survey of regional companies, which contributes to an overall evaluation of the regions' future potentials and the last step (WT2.3) – training sessions.

3 very nice steps

Ukrainian National Forestry University. Department of the furniture and wooden articles technology

MAIN IDEA of the WP2 - a detailed analysis of the forest sector

Ukrainian National Forestry University. Department of the furniture and wooden articles technology

MAIN IDEA of the WP2 - a detailed analysis of the forest sector

Methodology elaboration

3-level analysis carrying out

National

Regional

Enterprise

Methodological support

Objectives of WP2

O2.1 Evaluation of the regional forest-wood-sectors' competitiveness and resource efficiency

O2.2 Straightforward evaluation method for companies to assess resource efficiency of their production

O2.3 Upgrading and training of key players for performing baseline analysis in the ENP target countries

Task 2.1: Transnational training sessions and feedback for regional expert focus groups

- Transnational training sessions for regional experts
- Adaptation and adjustments of the survey guidelines to specificities in ENP eastern countries
- Final workshop on the lessons learned

Task 2.2: Survey ‘Self Assessment of wood-working enterprises on saving potentials for wood raw material use and energy consumption’

A simplified, easily applicable method to assess wood resources efficiency on the company level is developed. It builds on a questionnaire and a calculation tool, which can be applied by company owners themselves to evaluate their own performance of material and energy use in economic terms.

- **Wood resource use.**
- **Modern technology.**
- **Life-cycle-management.**
- **Innovative activity of enterprise.**
- **Obstacles and difficulties.**

Task 2.3: Current state and future outlook on the regional forest-wood sector's resource potential

- i) **Regional Resource Use.**
- ii) **Players.**
- iii) **Market Position.**
- iv) **Resource Efficiency Potentials.**
- v) **Conclusion and Recommendations.**

Outputs

1. Global sectorial analysis of the forestry-woodworking-chain in the ENP eastern regions
2. Collection of comparable data on raw material efficiency across enterprises and regions
3. Enhanced competence of research partners and key players in regional baseline analysis
4. Key figures, conclusions and recommendations for decision-makers in industry and public authority

Deliverables (month of delivery)

- D2.1** Transnational trainings of experts - Summary report **(M06)**
D2.2 Self-assessment of wood-working enterprises' saving potentials - Survey report **(M10)**
D2.3 Resource efficiency of the forestry and woodworking sector in ENP eastern countries - Final report **(M17)**

Our expectations from project and the consortium members

$$\text{DISAPPOINTMENT} = \frac{\text{EXPECTATION}}{\text{REALITY}}$$

Our expectations from project and the consortium members

In regard to WP2 we expect timely performance of all members' duties through caring out such points :

1. Adaptation and adjustments of the survey guidelines.
2. Global survey of forest-wood sectors.
3. Self- assessment at the enterprises level.

In regard to RERAM we expect:

1. Improving of the wood recourses usage effectiveness at the enterprises level (self-assessment, training for trainers, regional and national round tables, new clusters creation, real check).
2. Improving of the national (regional) forest-wood sectors functioning (global survey, regional and national round tables, recommendations and conclusions).
3. **NEW IDEAS AND NEW PROJECTS.**

Next steps in regard to WP 2

- 1. All countries-participants of RERAM project have specified all features for their surveys and self-assessment fulfillment till the end of M4 (September, 2014).**
- 2. Common methodology finally agreed till the end of M5 (October, 2014).**
- 3. All countries-participants of RERAM project have completed their self-assessment till the end of M7 (December, 2014).**
- 4. All countries-participants of RERAM project have completed their surveys till the end of M12 (May, 2015).**
- 5. Self-assessment report completed till the end of M9 (February, 2015) and Baseline report completed till the end of M15 (August, 2015).**

Discussion and conclusions

Ukrainian National Forestry University. Department of the furniture and wooden articles technology

Thank you for your attention!

Prof. Orest Kiyko
Ukrainian National Forestry University (UNFU)
Head of the furniture and wooden articles
technology Department
<http://www.tvd.org.ua/en/koa-main-en.htm>
nluzavtvd@txnet.com

Ukrainian National Forestry University. Department of the furniture and wooden articles technology

WP2 - Regional Baselines in Resource and Raw Material Efficiency Training

RERAM

BRIDGING GAPS BETWEEN R2I IN RESOURCE EFFICIENCY AND RAW MATERIALS

FP7-INCO Coordination Project 2014-2015

Kick-Off Meeting – Munster (14-17.07.2014)

Prof. Orest Kiyko

Ukrainian National Forestry University (UNFU)
Head of the furniture and wooden articles
technology Department

Contents

1. **Baseline survey (approach, methodology, example).**
2. **Discussion.**
3. **Agreed common approach, next steps, timeline.**
4. **Self assessment (approach, methodology, example).**
5. **Discussion.**
6. **Agreed common approach, next steps, timeline.**

MAIN IDEA of the GLOBAL SURVEY – a detailed analysis of the forest-wood sector

1. **Forest-wood sector identification.**
2. **Wood resources of this sector identification.**
3. **Identifications of the main players of this sector.**
4. **Determination of the forest sector “+” and “-”.**
5. **Conclusion and recommendations in regard to effectiveness of the wood usage.**

Some input points for baseline survey performing.

1. There are two levels of baseline survey - ***NATIONAL AND REGIONAL LEVELS.***
2. National analyses will be performed for MD, UA, GE (subject for discussion).
3. Regional analyses will be performed for UA (subject for discussion).
4. A global sectorial analysis of the forest-wood-chain is carried out based on existing sources of information (statistics, research literature, market surveys, project reports).

National baseline survey

1. Forest sector (forest-wood-chain) identifying

Structure of the forest sector

Number of the "forest" subindustry	Name of the "forest" subindustry according EU classification (NACE)	Name of the "forest" subindustry according UA classification (KVED)
Forestry subsector		
1	Forestry (02)	Forestry (02)
Solid wood subsector		
2	Wood products (20.1)	-
3	Sawmilling (20.1)	Sawmilling (20.1)
4	Wood-based panels (20.2)	Wood-based panels (20.2)
5	Wood construction (20.3)	Wood construction (20.3)
6	Wood packaging (20.4)	Wood packaging (20.4)
7	Misc. wood products (20.5)	Misc. wood products (20.5)
Furniture subsector		
8	Furniture (36.1)	Furniture (36.1)
Carpentry subsector		
9	Wood crafts (45x)	-
10	Carpentry (45.22.3)	Carpentry (45.22.0)
11	Joinery (45.42)	Joinery (45.42.0)
12	Parquet laying (45.43.1)	-
13	Wood trade (5x)	-
Cellulose subsector		
14	Paper products (21)	Paper products (21)
15	Paper production (21.1)	Paper production (21.1)
16	Paper articles (21.2)	Paper articles (21.2)
17	Publishing, printing (22)	Publishing, printing (22)
18	Publishing (22.1)	Publishing (22.1)
19	Printing (22.2)	Printing (22.2)

1. Forest sector (forest-wood-chain) identifying

Structure of the forest sector (for RERAM)

Number of the "forest" subindustry	Name of the "forest" subindustry
Forestry subsector	
1	Forestry (02)
Solid wood subsector	
2	Woodworking industry (16) including: Sawmilling (16.1) and Manufacturing of products from wood, cork, straw and plaiting materials (16.2)
Furniture subsector	
3	Furniture manufacturing (31)
Carpentry subsector	
4	Installing of the wood products (43.32) +Flooring and wall covering (43.33) +Roofing (43.91)

2. Main parameters of the national forest sector determine

Main parameters of the national forest sector

Main parameters of the national forest sector	Year	Name of the "forest" subindustry				Totally for national forest sector
		Forestry (02)	Woodworking industry (16)	Furniture manufacturing (31)	Installing of the wood products (43.32) +Flooring and wall covering (43.33) +Roofing (43.91)	
1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Turnover, bil. EUR						
Number of enterprises, units	2008 - 2012					
Number of employees, ths. persons						

3. National wood resources analysis

It is suggested to determine the following main parameters within the national wood resources analysis: **square of the forest land, overall timber stock, forest land percentage, forest property structure, average annual timber growth per hectare, overall annual timber growth for country, percentage of annual timber growth usage, procurement of merchantable wood (2008-2012), wood output, sawn or split (2008-2012), harvesting of marketable wood structure (2012), wooden wastes generation and utilization (2011-2012).**

3. National wood resources analysis

Wood resources

Index's number	Index's name	Index's value
1	Square of the forest land, million hectares	
2	Overall timber stock, billion m ³	
3	Forest land percentage, %	
4	Average annual timber growth per hectare, m ³ per hectare	
5	Overall annual timber growth for country, million m ³	
6	Percentage of annual timber growth usage, %	

Year	Index's value		Wood output, sawn or split, more than 6 mm wide, ths m ³
	Procurement of merchantable wood, ths m ³		
	Total value	Including main felling	
2008			
2009			
2010			
2011			
2012			

3. National wood resources analysis

Harvesting of marketable wood structure (2012)

Index's name	Index's value
Procurement of merchantable wood, ths m ³	
Round timber (from total procurement), ths m ³	
Including:	
for sawn timber	
for the plywood and veneer production	
for building	
for pulp and paper production	
Wood for technological purposes, ths m ³	
Firewood	

Wooden wastes generation and utilization, ths tons

Year	Generated ¹	Utilized, processed	Incinerated to generate energy
2011			
2012			

4. National forest sector contribution to the national industry

It is suggested to determine the place (share, contribution) of the national forest sector in regard to the national industry. In order to do that we suggest:

- to determine **turnover and number of employees for leading national subindustries** (e.g. extractive industry, production of food products, drunk and wares of tobaccos, light industry, production of coke, products of oil redoing, chemical and petrochemical industry, metallurgical production and production of the finished metallic products, machine building, production and distributing of electric power, gas and water and others);
- to compare **turnover, number of enterprises and number of employees for overall national forest sector and leading national subindustries for the period from 2011 to 2012;**
- to determine the national forest sector's share to the national GDP.

4. National forest sector contribution to the national industry

Turnover of the main subindustries

Subindustry's name	Turnover, mil. UAH	Percentage, %
Electric power, gas, water		
Metallurgy, hard wares		
Food products, drinks, wares of tobaccos		
Extractive industry		
Machine building		
Coke, products of oil industry		
Chemical industry		
Other non-metal mineral products		
Forest sector		
Light industry		

4. National forest sector contribution to the national industry

4. National forest sector contribution to the national industry

National GDP and forest sector's turnover

Year	GDP, mil. UAH	Turnover of the forest sector, mil. UAH	Share of the forest sector to GDP, %
2008			
2009			
2010			
2011			
2012			

5. Forest sectors main players identifying

It is suggested to identify the main players in the forest-wood sector and assess their capacities and linkages (e.g. **authorities, wood industries, suppliers, research bodies, supporting institutions, forest administration, consultants, entrepreneurs in harvesting, transportation, trade**).

6. Market Position identifying

It is suggested to evaluate the forest-wood-sector profile, identify gaps/opportunities, compare it against the national/international state-of-the-art, explore new market opportunities (e.g. **SWOT**).

7. Resource Efficiency Potentials determine and elaborating of the Conclusions and Recommendations

It is suggested:

- to synthesize innovation potentials for more effective wood resources use that could have a strong impact on national resource efficiency within the low carbon economy;
- to conclude policy-relevant findings and recommendations to decision-makers on the national level.

Regional baseline survey

Choice of the region for regional forest sector analysis

It is suggested to choose region for the regional forest sector analysis taking into consideration the following aspects:

- wood resources of the region;
- perspectives of the region in reference to regional forest sector development;
- relations and links of the RERAM participant in the certain country to the regional issues and regional problems solving;
- geographical regional placement of certain RERAM participant.

Ukraine will carry out regional analysis using mentioned above methodology determining regional indexes and comparing them with national ones.

The Carpathian region of Ukraine

Moldova and **Georgia** (if needed) will identify some regional forest sectors features (e.g. wood species, mountain areas existing, forest land percentage, wood resources, industrial development, market conditions and others) and on the base of the comparison (national and regional) will draw some conclusions in regard to regional wood-forest sectors perspectives.

List of possible data sources

1. International.
 - a. <http://www.unece.org/forests.html>
 - b. <http://www.forestplatform.org/en/>
 - c. <http://www.efi.int/portal/>
 - d. <http://www.cei-bois.org/>
 - e. <http://www.fao.org/forestry/en/>
 - f. http://ec.europa.eu/enterprise/sectors/furniture/index_en.htm
 - g. http://ec.europa.eu/enterprise/sectors/wood-paper-printing/index_en.htm
2. RERAM project.
 - a. https://www.dropbox.com/home/RERAM_exchange_folder/WP2_Regional_Baselines_UNFU/1_Common_methodology
 - b. https://www.dropbox.com/home/RERAM_exchange_folder/WP2_Regional_Baselines_UNFU/2_Knowledge_Base
 - c. <https://www.reram.eu>
3. Internal for each country
 - a. National statistic Committee.
 - b. National Forestry/Woodworking/Furniture associations.
 - c. National surveys.
 - d. Regional surveys.
 - e. All available reports.

National and Regional baseline surveys – Ukraine's example

Discussion and conclusions

Some points for discussion.

1. Conditional (for RERAM project) forest sector structure.
2. Necessity to carry out a global analysis at the national and regional levels.
3. The set of the parameters which will characterize the national/regional forest sectors development.
4. The time period for the global analyses carrying out.
5. The index's set for the international comparison.

Agreed common approach in regard to global survey

1. For RERAM project we will use UNFU definition of the forest sector (p. I.1 of UNFU methodology).
2. All countries-participants of RERAM project will be involved in the global survey fulfillment.
 - National analyses will carry out Ukraine, Moldova and Georgia.
 - Regional analysis will carry out only Ukraine as the largest ENP country. Moldova and Georgia will identify some features for the regional forest sectors development.
 - EU countries (AT, DE, PL) will determine main parameters of the national and regional forest sectors (p. II.2 of UNFU methodology) in order to compare them respectively with ENP ones.
3. We will use as a basic the set of the parameters according to p. II.2 of UNFU methodology.
4. We will use 5-years period (from 2008 to 2012) for the global analyses carrying out.
5. All countries-participants of RERAM project can add some supplementary points in their global surveys in the event of the necessity.

Next steps in regard to global survey

1. All countries-participants of RERAM project have specified all features for their surveys fulfillment till the end of M4 (September, 2014).
2. All countries-participants of RERAM project have completed their national surveys till the end of M6 (November, 2014).
3. All countries-participants of RERAM project have completed their regional surveys till the end of M8 (January, 2015).
4. On-line web-conference has conducted (for final adjustment and comparison among EU and ENP) till the end of M10 (March, 2015).
5. All countries-participants of RERAM project have completed their surveys till the end of M12 (May, 2015).
6. Baseline analyses completed till the end of M15 (August, 2015).

Thank you for your attention!

Prof. Orest Kiyko
Ukrainian National Forestry University (UNFU)
**Head of the furniture and wooden articles
technology Department**
<http://www.tvd.org.ua/en/koa-main-en.htm>
nluzavtvd@txnet.com

WP2 - Regional Baselines In Resource And Raw Material Efficiency

T2.2 - Survey 'Self Assessment of wood-working enterprises on saving potentials for wood raw material use and energy consumption'

RERAM

Bridging Gaps between R2I in
Resource Efficiency and **RAw** Material

FP7-INCO Coordination Project 2014-2015

Roman Shchupakivskyy

Ukrainian National Forestry University, Lviv, Ukraine

Department of Sawmilling, Joinery and Wooden Building Products

CONTENTS

1. The main aims of the survey
2. Self-assessment methodology:
 - approach → implementation;
 - expected outcomes
3. Example of the questionnaire
 - questionnaire design;
 - how to work with questionnaire
4. Calculation tool [key performance indicators]
5. Discussion
6. Agreed common approach [next steps → timeline]

1. The main objective and principles of the survey

It is suggested to consider a **Self-Assessment** of wood-working enterprises like a part of global **Baseline Survey**

- 3

2. Self-Assessment methodology

Main approach → Implementation → Outcomes

(single-step execution – 5 main steps):

- 4

2. Self-Assessment methodology

- 5

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Questionnaire of the international project RERAM*

Date Country Name of enterprise

Type(s) of products

The number of employees (persons totally): 2010 2011 2012
including workers: 2010 2011 2012

Wood raw materials used: round timber technical raw stock lumber
 workpieces wooden board materials sliced veneer

The share of wood in relation to the total volume processed, (%) hardwood softwood

The average volume of treated wood raw materials for the year, (m³)
round timber technical raw stocks lumber
workpieces wooden board materials sliced veneer

I. Efficient use of wooden raw materials

1.1 Do you know how much wood waste is thrown (wasted) every year in your country?
 no yes, (thousand m³/ million m³)

1.2 Point out the turnover (thousand €)*2 made from wooden raw materials in: 2010 2011 2012

1.3 Point out the total cost (thousand €) of wooden raw materials (round logs, technical raw stock, lumber, workpieces, wooden board materials and veneer) expended in the production of turnover in:
2010 2011 2012

1.4 Point out the value (thousand €) of main profile product*3 types sailed in 2012:
A) B) C)

1.5 Point out the volume of wooden raw material (m³) processed in:
2010 2011 2012

1.6 Point out the total cost (thousand €) of wooden raw materials (round logs, technical raw stock, timber, workpieces, wooden board materials and veneer), expended in the production of basic profile types of the realized products in 2012: A) B) C)

1.7 Point out the total amount of wood wastes in the technological process according to the types of:
A) lump waste tones / or m³
B) sawdust shavings tones / or m³

* - Please mark your choice (V), or write a response in the appropriate field in the forms;
*2 - Yearly average exchange euro rates; *3 - A, B, C and others - main profile product types.

1.8 Point out:

A) Approximated percentage of the useful output of sawn timber at the stage of primary processing, (%)

B) The average percentage of useful output of finished products at the stage of secondary processing, (%)

1.9 Point out:

A) used as a fuel tones

B) disposed off tones

C) sold to the outside tones

D) removed to specially designated areas or objects tones

1.10 Point out the number of employees engaged in the gathering and recycling of wooden wastes persons

1.11 Point out the percentage of the use of wooden wastes (the ratio of the used at the enterprise waste amount to their total volume) %

1.12 Do you make a cost estimation of wood wastes in the recycling process?
 no yes (how exactly)

1.13 Do you buy a wooden wastes on the market?
 no yes

1.14 Have you considered directions of reducing material consumption of wood products?

by increasing the share of substitute materials

by increasing the share of recyclable wooden raw material (chipboard, MDF, etc.)

other option

1.15 How much you could reduce the cost of production of wood provided effective management?

5% 10% 15% 20% 25% more (indicate how much)

1.16 Are you interested in training sessions to improve the efficient use of wood raw materials?

no yes

II. Modern technologies

2.1 The number of units of technological equipment installed at your enterprise units

2.2 Point out: the average age of the equipment at your enterprise (years), and the average degree of equipment deterioration %

2.3 Point out the existing quality management model at your Company:

certified quality system according to ISO or other standart

- preparation for the products quality certification is going on
- there is a multilevel product control by technical control service
- we apply a periodic testing of products
- we apply a self-control system at working places (jobs)

2.4 What sanctions do you apply at your Company for the low-quality products production?

2.5 Point out the type of aspiration system at your enterprise:

- conce-through system
 - permanent
 - periodic
- recirculation system
 - general exchange system
 - self-supporting (with captor hoods)
- none at all

2.6 Are there modern technologies at your enterprise?
 no yes (wich exactly)

III. Life cycle assessment of products

3.1 Products design and development at your Company is:

- based on the own sketches creating (design Bureau)
- borrowed from exhibitions
- based on the products catalogs
- according to individual orders

3.2 Do you use software for products construction design?
 no yes (wich exactly)

3.3 Do you predict a products recycling after the end of its life cycle?
 no yes

3.4 What goals do you predict for the wooden material using after the end of product life cycle?
 as an energy source
 by recycling of used wood and its secondary use

3.5 Do you use the assessment of products life cycle?
 in designing
 in marketing

IV. Energy efficiency

4.1 Point out the type and number of drying equipment units that is used at your enterprise:

- convection kilns
 - roller driers
 - rotary drum driers
 - conventional dry kilns
 - belt drying kilns
- vacuum kiln
- steaming chambers
- heat treatment kilns

4.2 Point out the heat carrier type in heating system:

- water
- superheated steam (overheated steam)
- high-temperature heat carriers (diathermal oil, glycol, etc.)

4.3 What is the average annual indicator of heat and electricity using for production needs?

Gcal kWt

4.4 Indicate the availability of energy saving systems at your enterprise:

- heat recovery using recuperative heat exchanger:
 - heat recovery wheel
 - plate type
- variable frequency drive systems
- vacuum aspiration system
- bivalent heating installation with a heat pump
- solar heated lumber dry kiln
- none of the above mentioned
- other

4.5 Are you interested in training sessions to improve the energy efficiency of your enterprise?

no yes

V. Innovative activity of the enterprise

5.1 Are you aware of innovations in your industry and the revenues that they can provide?

- yes
- no
- not interested in this

5.2 Is it conducted at your Company project-design, technological, research efforts and activities for the new ideas in the production process implementation ?

- yes, search is carried out periodically
 on the basis of personal initiative with further remuneration
 no

5.3 What kind of innovative technologies do you apply at the enterprise ?

- domestic
 foreign

5.4 Point out the specialized software or computer complex systems for automated technological operations:

stage of the technological process complex or software
 stage of the technological process complex or software
 stage of the technological process complex or software

5.5 Have you analyzed the efficiency of wood details substitution in the manufacturing process for the details made from such material?

- metal profile
 glass-mirror
 edge material
 other

5.6 Does the assortment of your Company products include a unique (innovative) within the framework of?

- Ukraine
 Europe
 overall world

5.7 Does your Company on the creation of the innovate products ?

- yes no

5.8 Are you interested in training sessions on implementation of innovations at your enterprise?

- yes no

VI. Obstacles and difficulties

6.1 Do you see any obstacles for the development of your enterprise (underline)?

- | | |
|--|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> shortage of raw materials | <input type="checkbox"/> the high price of raw materials |
| <input type="checkbox"/> lack of specialists | <input type="checkbox"/> insufficient qualification of the specialists |
| <input type="checkbox"/> access to sales markets | <input type="checkbox"/> competition |
| <input type="checkbox"/> legislative restrictions | <input type="checkbox"/> access to credits and investments |
| <input type="checkbox"/> access to credits and investments | <input type="checkbox"/> bureaucratic barriers |

- high taxation and not stability of tax legislation
 difficulties in finding of the partner companies
 the complicated conditions of the tender (the sale of raw materials)
 the shortage (deficiency) of circulating assets for purchase of raw materials
 other

6.2 Which ways of underlined above problems solving do you see ?

6.3 What are the main tasks for your Company for the next years (specify not more than three answers)?

- | | |
|--|---|
| <input type="checkbox"/> increasing the expences of labor payment | <input type="checkbox"/> increasing the production volumes |
| <input type="checkbox"/> improving the raw materials sawing | <input type="checkbox"/> improving the energy efficiency |
| <input type="checkbox"/> products certification | <input type="checkbox"/> production processes certification |
| <input type="checkbox"/> solving a problems of waste management | <input type="checkbox"/> improvement of quality products |
| <input type="checkbox"/> improvement of production promotion policy of the enterprise | |
| <input type="checkbox"/> mastering of new technologies/equipment and introduction of innovations | |
| <input type="checkbox"/> increasing of number and improving the qualification of employees | |
| <input type="checkbox"/> improvement of planning and accounting systems of the enterprise | |
| <input type="checkbox"/> consultative and informational assistance in finding suppliers and manufacturers of the equipment | |
| <input type="checkbox"/> a new assortment of products introduction (which one) <input type="text"/> | |
| <input type="checkbox"/> solving the problems in reference to sales of products on the market (point out which one) <input type="text"/> | |
| <input type="checkbox"/> other <input type="text"/> | |

6.4 What kind of support would help you in developing your business?

- informational (access to relevant information)
 innovative (implementation of innovations in production)
 training support :
 on certain aspects of business complex management

6.5 Please state which fields of efficiency management have the highest priority for your business development?

- raw materials supply
 material use in product developmet
 energy water waste

We sincerely thank you for cooperation and understanding !

Save Form

Print Form

Submit by email

Reset Form

5. Calculation tool

▪ The main indicators for raw materials and resource efficiency use

Nº	INDICATOR	CONTENT
1	Raw material productivity (€/m ³)	Sales per 1 m ³ of processed wood raw materials
2	The percentage of useful output (%)	Volume of output per 1 m ³ of processed wood raw materials
3	The percentage of wastes use (%)	Used wood wastes per 1 m ³ of their common quantity
4	Losses from wastes (€)	The difference between wood wastes value by wood raw materials average prices and their value by wastes assessment
5	Complexity of processing of 1 m ³ of raw materials (man-hours/ m ³)	Labour quantity per 1 m ³ of processed wood raw materials
6	Complexity of effectiveness processing of raw materials (man-hours/%)	Labour quantity per 1% of useful output
7	Labor productivity of 1 employer (m ³ /person)	Sales per 1 employer
8	Turnover of energy productivity (€/kWh of electricity)	Energy productivity
9	Energy thrift (kWh of electricity/ m ³)	The amount spent on the production of electricity per 1 m ³ of processed wood raw materials

5. Calculation tool

▪ Comparing of Indicators

Internal and external benchmarking approach:

1. enterprises of separate countries regional level between each other;
2. defined enterprises and national level survey results;
3. enterprises and ENP-country level;
4. ENP-country enterprises with EU-leading enterprises level.

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5. Some points for discussion

1. Should we develop separate questionnaires for particular subsectors of woodworking?
2. How many enterprises should we chose for survey at the regional level?
3. Is it advisable to conduct surveys in all project partner countries or only in the countries of the Eastern Partnership?
4. Is it advisable to change (add) chapters of questionnaire?
5. Will this questionnaire execute the basic requirements of the project?
6. Are there too much technical questions in the survey?
7. Are there confidential data in the questionnaire that can be not granted by the enterprises

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6. Agreed common approach

6. Agreed common approach

THANK YOU FOR YOUR ATTENTION !

RERAM

Bridging Gaps between R2I in
Resource Efficiency and RAW Material

FP7-INCO Coordination Project 2014-2015

Roman Shchupakivskyy

Ukrainian National Forestry University, Lviv, Ukraine

Department of Sawmilling, Joinery and Wooden Building Products

RERAM

research to innovation in
resource efficiency

EU FP7 project no. 609573
01/06/2014-31/05/2016
www.reram.eu

Training Week Lviv Minutes

Date

Monday, 13 Oct – Friday, 17 Oct 2014

Venue

Astoria Hotel

15 Horodotska St., 79007 Lviv, Ukraine

prepared by

Orest Kiyko (UNFU)

Roman Shchupakivskyy (UNFU)

Ukrainian National Forestry University
Gen. Tchuprynka str., 103, 79057, Lviv, Ukraine
Tel: +38 032 238 45 04
<http://tvd.org.ua>

List of participants

Nr	Beneficiary	Attendant (First name, surname)
01	IIWH, Germany	Uwe Kies
02	HCS, Austria	Roland Oberwimmer
03	HCS, Austria	Matthias Kolck
04	HCS, Austria	Visnja Jurnjak
05	HCS, Austria	Thomas Dielacher
06	HCS, Austria	Christian Angerbauer
07	ITD, Poland	Magdalena Herbec
08	ITD, Poland	Ewa Leszczyszyn
09	UNFU, Ukraine	Orest Kiyko
10	UNFU, Ukraine	Myroslava Yakuba
11	UNFU, Ukraine	Roman Shchupakivskyy
12	UNFU, Ukraine	Ivan Voytovych
13	FORZA, Ukraine	Lesya Loyko
14	FORZA, Ukraine	Nataliya Voloshyn
15	FORZA, Ukraine	Radmilla Ustych
16	FORZA, Ukraine	Yuriy Derbal
17	WPFC, Ukraine	Volodymyr Vorobey
18	AITT, Moldova	Vadim Iatchevici
19	RECC, Georgia	Sophiko Akhobadze
20	AUG, Georgia	Teimuraz Kandelaki
21	AUG, Georgia	Mamuka Khoshtaria
22	INNOVAWOOD, Belgium	Gus Verhaege
23	PROKO, Austria	Harald Suitner
24	WPFC, Ukraine	Volodymyr Popovych
25	WPFC, Ukraine	Kateryna Kravchuk
26	MEES Development, Ukraine	Roman Kuzyk

red = reference to presentations (numbered) or documents on CD-Rom and in shared folder.

DAY 1 / MONDAY, 13.10.2014

Time	Activity, Presentation
09:00	<p>WP2 Coordination: UNFU, Prof. Orest Kiyko</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Welcome by Prof. O. Kyiko > (Lviv meeting introduction Orest Kiyko.ppt) : <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Welcome words; - RERAM Introduction; - Introduction of participants ; - Introduction of the training program. <p>Coordinator's introduction and overview: IIWH, Dr. Uwe Kies :</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Incoming about objectives and the aim of the project; - The main expectations of Training week in Lviv and RERAM project overall.
09:20	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ A brief representation of trainers: Mr. Thomas Dielacher, Mr. Christian Angerbauer. ▪ Introduction of partners - short oral presentation of the participants: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - RECC, Georgia: Sophiko Akhobadze; - FORZA, Carpathia / Ukraine: Lesya Loyko; - ITD, Poland: Ewa Leszczyszyn, Magdalena Herbec; - AUG, Georgia: Mamuka Khoshtaria; - PROKO: Harald Suitner; - HCS, Austria: Matthias Kolck; - FORZA, Carpathia / Ukraine: Yuriy Debral - AITT, Moldova: Vadim Iatchevici; - UNFU, Lviv: Ivan Voytovych, Myroslava Yakuba, Orest Kiyko; - FORZA, Carpathia / Ukraine: Radmila Ustych, Nataliya Voloshyna - Woodworking company manager (WPFC Group) / Ukraine: Roman Kuzyk; - HCS, Styria/Austria : Roland Oberwimmer, Visnja Jurnjak.
10:00	<p>WP6 Coordination: FORZA, Lesya Loyko</p> <p>Discussion of administrative matters and issues relating to the organization of the Training Week, workshops and stay in Lviv (in accordance with agenda) > (2014-10-13_RERAM_Agenda_Training_Week_Lviv.pdf).</p>

10:15	Break
10:30	WS1 Start. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Interactive input on Cleaner Production and Resource Efficiency - Thomas Dielacher. > (1.2 Sustainable management mind-set values action.ppt).
11:00	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Cleaner Production vs. End of Pipe – Thomas Dielacher, Christian Angerbauer > (1.3 CP vs End of the Pipe1.ppt). <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Main idea of cleaner production (CP); - Connections between CP and ECO-Efficiency; - Principles of input / output – analysis, material flow analysis, energy analysis; - Input/output balance; - Introduction to the Material flow analysis as a detailed description of the material- and energy uses <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ <i>(Example with the consumption of paint on the furniture company);</i> - Strategies for CP-Options; - Possible barriers for implementation of CP options <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ <i>(Exercise - Definition of each of the training participants percentage between existing barriers to the introduction of cleaner production in the company. Discussion of results.)</i>
12:00	Lunch in Astoria Hotel
13:30	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ CP Options/Examples - Christian Angerbauer > (1.4 CP OPTIONS in general1.ppt). <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Detailed analysis of the Strategies for Waste Minimization with the examples of its implementation on the real woodworking enterprises. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ <i>Examples of: - good housekeeping (optimisation of pumps of drying chamber and compressor system, operating hours of conveyors and machines, aircon optimisation, optimisation of packaging); - new materials and technologies using, - waste recovery, etc.</i>
14:20	<p>In the discussion the following point are highlighted:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Lesya Loyko - the issue of economic efficiency of translucent windows on the roof of industrial woodworking buildings (installation costs and ongoing maintenance of washing, etc.); ▪ Volodymyr Vorobey – about spreading of the trends to lease certain items of equipment (tankers for paint storage, varnish, etc.) on wood-processing enterprises; ▪ Orest Kiyko - inability to use the “Finger Jointing” as new technologies; ▪ Mamuka Khoshtaria– about the possibility of resource efficiency and

	environmental performance at the enterprises by distillation of some liquid waste, including paint, etc. and their partial secondary use.
15:45	Remarks on organizational and administrative matters - Lesya Loyko. All presentation materials of this training and tasks for the exercises, answers, etc. will be in the open access for all participants in a bilingual version.
16:00	Coffee break
16:15	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Exercise on Mini Case Studies - Thomas Dielacher, Christian Angerbauer > (1.5 Input on mini case studies1.ppt). <p>Task #2 > (1.5 Mini case studies tasks.doc) :</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Introduction to the basic objectives of the tasks and principles of its holding. Breakup of the training participants for three working groups. Start on the task 2 – “residual yoghurt used”. ▪ As a result of working on the task, each group expressed their vision for the Strategies for CP-Options, and possible approaches to solving this problem. ▪ Public verbal presentation of the results of group leaders: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Lesya Loyko (Group #1) – “The combined strategy: Waste minimizations - Reduction of the source - Process modification - Good housekeeping and New technologies”. 2. Roland Oberwimmer (Group #2) – “Waste minimizations - Reduction of the source – Product modification – Select new materials”. 3. Uwe Kies (Group #3) – “Strategy: Waste minimizations - Reduction of the source - Process modification - Good housekeeping and New technologies”. ▪ Discussion of the results of work on the task. Explanation of false steps in choosing strategies of CP-option.
16:45	<p>Task #5 > (1.5 Mini case studies tasks.doc) :</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Group work on practical task # 5 of the training (“empty containers for the detergents”); ▪ Public verbal presentation of the results of group leaders: (Uwe Kies, Roland Oberwimmer, Sophiko Akhobadze).
17:15	In-depth study of the work on the tasks. Analysis of mistakes in approaches to Strategies for CP-options selection - Thomas Dielacher, Christian Angerbauer.
17:30	Closure and End of Training Week / Day 1st.

DAY 2 / TUESDAY, 14.10.2014

Time	Activity, Presentation
08:50	Start of Excursion day to woodworking enterprises in Lviv region. Meeting lobby Astoria Hotel; Bus drive to FAKRO.
09:30	Excursion point 1: FAKRO-LVIV > (RERAM_photo_exchange) <p data-bbox="759 607 1412 680">FAKRO-Lviv (79040, Lviv, Gorodotska Street 355b, www.fakro.com.ua , www.fakro.com)</p> <p data-bbox="759 689 1412 958">Study tour of wood processing industry enterprise (window producer). Most dynamic and fastest growing roof window manufacturer in the world. The co-owners of international subsidiaries are trading in: UK, Austria, Spain, the Netherlands, Ireland, Germany, Poland, Russia and Hungary. Subsidiary company in Lviv "FAKRO-Lviv".</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <li data-bbox="365 1010 1412 1122">▪ Brief introductory speech by the chief engineer Mr. Andriy Martynyak about the history of the company, specialization and its specifics of production. <li data-bbox="365 1131 1412 1514">▪ Guided tour through the main production areas of enterprise headed by director Mr. Yevstakhiy Koronchevskyy and chief engineer: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <li data-bbox="424 1216 767 1249">- Raw-material storage; <li data-bbox="424 1258 751 1292">- Sawmill department; <li data-bbox="424 1301 735 1335">- Drying department; <li data-bbox="424 1344 935 1377">- Boiler house and air blowing room; <li data-bbox="424 1386 1412 1420">- Department of primary and secondary mechanical processing of wood; <li data-bbox="424 1429 1102 1462">- Lines of roof windows and stairs manufacturing; <li data-bbox="424 1471 1326 1505">- Department of manning and packaging for the finished products. <li data-bbox="365 1570 1412 1899">▪ In the discussion the following point are highlighted: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <li data-bbox="424 1615 1412 1682">- Main strengths and weaknesses in the organization of the technological process at the enterprise; <li data-bbox="424 1691 983 1724">- Trends, methods and volumes of sales; <li data-bbox="424 1733 1412 1800">- The state of energy effectiveness and possible ways of improvements in this area; <li data-bbox="424 1809 1126 1843">- Problems with production and maintenance staff; <li data-bbox="424 1852 1302 1886">- Future plans of the company and ways of its improvement, etc.
11:15	Bus drive to BUK-HOLDING

11:30	<p>Excursion point 2: BUK-HOLDING > (RERAM_photo_exchange) BUK-HOLDING (79040, Lviv, Kurmanovycha Street 2, www.bukholding.com.ua/index.php/en).</p> <p>Study tour of wood processing industry enterprise. Buk-Holding Ltd. – is a Lviv-based company with a 16-years’ experience. Employees - 20. Buk-Holding provides the following products from wood: windows, doors, stairs and staircases, balusters, barriers, other small wooden items for interior design. All products are made by jointing of dried glued laminated timber from materials chosen by the customer (pine, beech, oak, mahogany) with conformance to all technological requirements.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Brief introductory remarks by the chief engineer about the history and specifics activity of the company. ▪ Training and familiarization tour through stages of the technological process: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - section of primary and secondary wood processing; - workshop of varnishing and painting; - plant for the manufacture of fuel briquettes; - auxiliary facilities (compressor house, boiler, etc.) ▪ Discussion and short summarizing by the coach (Mr. Christian Angerbauer) regarding resource and energy efficiency at the enterprise, focusing on weaknesses in the production process and housekeeping.
12:20	Bus drive to the Astoria Hotel
13:00	Common lunch with the SC members in Astoria restaurant
14:00	Bus drive from Lviv to Ivano-Frankove
14:45	<p>Excursion point 3: YURVIT > (RERAM_photo_exchange)</p> <p>YURVIT (81070, Lviv reg., Yavorivsky dist, v. Ivano-Frankove, Sichovyh Striltsiv St. 2a, http://yurvit.com.ua/uk/). Company was established in 1993 in Ukraine. Employees - 110. The company produces furniture from solid wood.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Brief introductory remarks by the director (owner) Mr. Vitaliy Gugus about the history and specifics activity of the company; ▪ Guided tour of furniture industry enterprise. Introduction to basic technological stages of production: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - storage location for sawn timber; - vacuum drying chambers;

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - section of veneering; - finishing workshop; - bending section; - department of manning, preparation and storage of finished products. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Joint discussion with director of the features of technological process at enterprise, problems and difficulties of production, etc.
16:20	Bus drive to PROFESSIONAL SCHOOL #17
16:30	<p>Excursion point 4: PROFESSIONAL SCHOOL # 17 > (RERAM_photo_exchange) PROFESSIONAL SCHOOL # 17 (81070, Ukraine, Lviv oblast, Yavorivsky district, v. Ivano-Frankove, Market square 13). PROFESSIONAL SCHOOL trains joiners and carpenters for local woodworking industry.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Welcome at the Museum by director Mr. Volodymyr Hevalo. ▪ Short introduction to the PROFESSIONAL SCHOOL and Museum ▪ Guided tour of museum of wood - http://hptu14.com.ua/prozaklad/muzei.html. ▪ Meeting with teachers and industry representatives: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - RERAM project goals and objectives (Mr. Volodymyr Vorobey) - Mr. Kiyko informs the representatives about relationship between the current state of the woodworking industry, problems of specialists trainings and the main objectives of the project.
17:45	Coffee break
18:15	Sightseeing tour of the temple fitted with wooden wares from professional school #17.
18:25	Closure and End of Training Week / Day 2 nd .
18:30	Bus drive to the Astoria Hotel, Lviv

DAY 3 / WEDNESDAY, 15.10.2014

Time	Activity, Presentation
09:00	WS2 Start. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Interactive input on Material flow analysis and case studies. Input on Initial Audit/Reality Check - Thomas Dielacher, Christian Angerbauer . <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Summary of WS 1 (incl. new Mini Case Study).
09:25	Task #4 > (1.5 Mini case studies tasks.doc) : <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Introduction to the basic objectives of the task and principles of it holding. Breakup of the training participants for two working groups. Start on the task 4 – “paper labels”. ▪ As a result of working on the task, each group expressed their vision for the Strategies for CP-Options, and possible approaches to solving this problem. ▪ Public verbal presentation of the results of group leaders (Matthias Kolck, Yuriy Derbal). ▪ Short discussion and analysis of chosen approach in each group (Thomas Dielacher, Christian Angerbauer)
10:15	Input on Material Flow Analysis (MFA) - Christian Angerbauer, Thomas Dielacher > (2.1 Material flow analysis1.ppt) : <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Main goals of a material flow analysis; - Choice of object analysis (materials); - Conducting a material flow analysis; <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ <i>Example: Material flows in a car repair paint shop: before and after optimization.</i> ▪ Q/A (Roland Oberwimmer) - What methods of measurement may be used in determining the costs of paint as shown in this example? (Christian Angerbauer) - We used a stepwise approach at each stage of production. However, usually when there is no possibility of analytically determination of costs they should be measured at all the stages. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Introduction to the step by step implementation of flow analysis.
10:45	Meeting with press with selected participants. Coffee break. Interviews, photos and video of speakers and RERAM partners by local press and UNFU PR team. > (see folders “RERAM_photo_exchange”)
12:00	Continuation of the training - analysis of technological process. Detailed explanation of MFA (MFA example) - Christian Angerbauer, Thomas Dielacher > (2.2 MFA results- Machino Plastics Ltd1.ppt). Questions/Answers (Q/A) as follows were discussed in detail : <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Q/A (Mamuka Khoshtaria) - Could you tell an approximate price for this class filter materials?

	<p>(Christian Angerbauer) - Using of filters is not too costly compared with the effect of savings painting materials. The main problem of production is not in lack of filters, but in the not-timeliness of their changes.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Q/A (Orest Kiyko) - The problem that the economic expectations of the economy is greater than the benefits. How to evaluate an investment in innovation if the payback period is large? <p>(Christian Angerbauer) – Of course it depends of your balance rate. But, if you want to apply it to the flow analysis, then you should operate reasonably. Because, if the effort and invested money in research of the issue is too big, and you do not know what will you really receive at the end, possibly you do not have invest.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Q/A (Vadim Iatchevici) - Could you show or describe this technological process in general? <p>(Thomas Dielacher) - This is completely new equipment, they had it but they did not have skilled people, which is why they did not use it. As a result of improved efficiency have been increased by approximately 40%.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Q/A (Mamuka Khoshtaria) - What is the recommended working pressure in the compressor? <p>(Christian Angerbauer) - Actually it should be not more than 10 psi. Recommended value is 7-10 psi.</p>
13:00	Lunch in Astoria restaurant
13:45	<p>MFA exercise 1 - Christian Angerbauer, Thomas Dielacher > (2.3 MFA results- SLD-I.ppt)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Material Flow Analysis - Injection molding machine example: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Involved stages; - Review and description of technological process; - Classification of the stages of scrap formation; - Review of Sankey diagram - Injection molding; - Searching for ways to process improvement; - Ultimate results; - Figures for controlling.
14:20	<p>MFA exercise 2 - Christian Angerbauer, Thomas Dielacher > (2.4 MFA Exercise1.ppt).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Introduction to the basic objectives of the task and principles of it holding. Breakup of the training participants for two working groups. Start on the Exercise #2 – “coffee machine”.

14:40	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Work on the task in two groups. Interpretation of the results on the graphs, and verbal explanation using MFA.
15:45	<p>Analysis of the results. Presentation of the MFA results (flow sheet of the process, overall balance, Sankey diagram for water, demonstration the composition of coffee-grounds and coffee using pie- or bar-charts). Guidelines for coffee cooking technology improving (main three proposals for improvement):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Group #1 (represent. Matthias Kolck, Visnja Jurnjak, Vadim Iatchevici) > Flipchart (IMG_5270.jpg). - Group #2 (represent. Uwe Kies, Natalia Voloshyn) > Flipchart (IMG_5271.jpg).
16:25	<p>Analysis of the accepted approaches, basic principles, errors and obtained results - Christian Angerbauer, Thomas Dielacher > (2.4 MFA Exercise1.ppt) :</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Case study scheme of coffee making; - Output of overall balance; - Example of Sankey diagram for water flow; - Few variants for coffee making – options.
16:40	A brief history about real “Coffee ceremony” – Ivan Voytovych.
17:00	Coffee break.
17:15	<p>Input on Initial Audit/Reality Check and tools - Christian Angerbauer > (2.6 Initial auditing1.ppt) :</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Main definitions and goals of an environmental audit; - Objectives for the initial RE audit; - The main requirements for a qualified auditor; - Interview steps and question techniques; - Schedule for an initial environmental audit; - What to look for and ask about in the first place; - Main requirements for audit outcomes
18:10	<p>Remarks (common rules) regarding the specific of Ukrainian woodworking enterprises technical audit - Orest Kiyko :</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Do not count on an understanding of the owner if we talk about sustainable development; - In most cases the directors of small woodworking enterprises are directly owners. - We must be ready for the next logic that sometimes exists among owners – “do not teach us to live and work, and teach us to earn or save money”;
18:30	Closure and End of Training Week / Day 3 rd .

DAY 4 / TUESDAY, 16.10.2014

Time	Activity, Presentation
08:30	Bus drive from Lviv to Stryi.
10:00	<p>Excursion point: FURNITURE STYLE</p> <p>FURNITURE STYLE (Lviv region, Stryisky district, v. Graboveth, Lopatynsky Street 141). "FURNITURE STYLE" (http://www.meblastil.com/) is private company established in Ukraine in 1997. The company produces furniture from solid wood. Employees – 110.</p>
10:15	Introduction to RERAM and the reality check (briefing, scope, goals) - Dr. Uwe Kies, Roland Oberwimmer.
10:30	<p>Welcome words by the owners (director) - Mr. Volodymyr Turchyn.</p> <p>Short Introduction of the company: history and development, the critical period of activity, the main profile and market niche development priorities. Main expectations of real check and participation in the RERAM project as a whole.</p>
11:00	Coffee break
11:15	<p>Walk through with questions and answers, in discussion with trainees and entrepreneur/technical staff > (RERAM_photo_exchange):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Exhibition hall of furniture products of the company; - General overview of all territory (manufacturing, administrative and auxiliary apartments); - Raw-material storage; - Drying department; - Department of cutting sawn timber into the workpieces; - Workshop for furniture frames manufacturing; - Department of foam rubber cutting; - House assembly of furniture; - Workshop of preparation and cutting upholstery tissues; - Testing laboratory; - Workshop for the furniture production from chipboard, etc. <p>Questions/Answers (Q/A) as follows were discussed in detail :</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Q/A (Yuriy Derbal) - Is there a need for heating the exhibition hall? (Volodymyr Turchyn) - Heating of exhibition halls is required, since the humidity of frame from solid will not change. Moreover exhibition hall of is permanent for customers. ▪ Q/A (Roland Oberwimmer) - Who is the visitor of the exhibition hall? (Volodymyr Turchyn) - Main target audience is customer with individual small order. ▪ Q/A (Roland Oberwimmer) - What is the cost of heat energy for this hall? (Volodymyr Turchyn) - We have only one measuring section of heat energy,

	<p>so the costs are aggregated for the enterprise at all.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Q/A (Thomas Dielacher) - How do you use wastes of sawmilling? (Volodymyr Turchyn) - All waste is burned solely in the boiler for the purpose of heating enterprises. ▪ Q/A (Christian Angerbauer) - how does the process of lumber during work? (Volodymyr Turchyn) - The process of convective drying is automated, supporting parameters of the drying agent and moisture content of wood. ▪ Q/A (Christian Angerbauer) - How much heat energy does drying complex consume? (Volodymyr Turchyn) - Approximately 100-110 kilowatts. It is about 10% of total consumption. ▪ Q/A (Uwe Kies) - What is the average duration of the drying process? (Volodymyr Turchyn) – Soft wood (mainly spruce) with the thickness of 25 millimetres dries in an average of 12-14 days. ▪ Q/A (Christian Angerbauer) - How often does warm water pumps operate? (Volodymyr Turchyn) - We have an automatic pump control system of the dryer. ▪ Q/A (Teimuraz Kandelaki) - Have you considered the possibility of using waste to produce souvenirs. (Volodymyr Turchyn) - Job costing shows that we do not have an excess of wooden waste. However, the main prospect for us, all the same, is finger jointing line. <p>Main remarks on the organization / arrangement of workshops and equipment:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Christian Angerbauer: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Positive of use energy saving lamps; - Excellent insulation window and door frames; - Regulation of heat is due to the thermostatic head; - No recuperates of heat energy at the inlet and exhaust ducts of dryer. ▪ Yuriy Debral: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - It is advisable to install the screens repel heat behind the radiators. ▪ Thomas Dielacher: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - There are many leaks in the construction of the drying chamber; - No frequency converters for motors of fans and water pumps; - Engines and equipment on sawmilling workshop are too noisy; - Impractical to turn on artificial lighting at the workplace in the day time; - It was inappropriate to install a line from the compressor to the sawmill workshop. Line is too long and pressure losses in the system is not justified. -
14:00	Lunch in Vulyk restaurant

15:15	<p>Continuation of walk through (with questions and answers, in discussion with trainees and entrepreneur/technical staff) > (RERAM_photo_exchange):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Boiler house; - Overview of aspiration and pneumatic systems; - Compressor station; - Electro panel and transformer substation; - Station of water supply, etc. <p>Questions/Answers (Q/A) as follows were discussed in detail :</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Q/A (Christian Angerbauer) - What is the averaged coolant temperature? (Volodymyr Turchyn) - Direct line 90°C, return line - 70°C. ▪ Q/A (Thomas Dielacher) - Is there current system of air recirculation? (Volodymyr Turchyn) - There is no recirculation branch. We could not use it in this type of aspiration equipment. ▪ Q/A (Christian Angerbauer) - What is the thickness of the insulation on the pipes in the boiler heating system? (Volodymyr Turchyn) - Pipe insulation 25-30mm. ▪ Q/A (Vadim Iatchevici) - Is there existing system of recycling the gases while burning? (Volodymyr Turchyn) - Unfortunately no. <p>Q/A (Thomas Dielacher) - What is the average pressure in the compressor? (Volodymyr Turchyn) - Within the limits of 6 bar.</p> <p>Q/A (Christian Angerbauer) - Is there current system of recirculation of exhaust air from the compressor to industrial premises? (Volodymyr Turchyn) - Returning of the air is missing. Exhaust air in winter is used to heat the compressor room to prevent condensation of oil. In summer heating of premises is not required.</p>
15:45	Coffee break
16:00	<p>Round table discussion of the issues of energy and resource efficiency in the enterprise (Mebli-Styl conference room).</p> <p>Group discussion/clarification of open questions :</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Q/A (Thomas Dielacher) - how do you determine the consumption of hot water and heat energy for workers? (Volodymyr Turchyn) - We use average indicators of consumption rate per one worker. ▪ Q/A (Christian Angerbauer) - Do you have enough domestic wood waste for heating? (Volodymyr Turchyn) - During the winter period we buy sawdust. ▪ Q/A (Yuriy Derbal) - Which is the source of water supply? (Volodymyr Turchyn) - We have our own water cleft for household needs. ▪ Q/A (Yuriy Derbal) -How do you control the level of sawdust in aspiration

	<p>bags? (Volodymyr Turchyn) - We have a hole at the bottom of the bag that indicate the level of of filling.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Q/A (Yuriy Derbal) - Have you tried to use night rate for electricity? (Volodymyr Turchyn) - We know from practice that use of labour work in night shifts is inappropriate and economically ineffective.
16:45	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Thomas Dielacher summarized the outcomes of the initial reality check, and first conclusion on potentials and options by the external experts. ▪ Christian Angerbauer announced the next important steps to come: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - writing a report about the state of resource and energy efficiency at the enterprise by external experts; - preliminary discussion of the reality check analysis in the form of video conferencing, etc.; - presenting the results of reality check in direct appointment with the responsible person at the company. ▪ Words of gratitude – Volodymyr Turchyn.
17:10	Closure and End of Training Week / Day 4 th . Bus drive back to Lviv.

DAY 5 / FRIDAY, 17.10.2014

Time	Activity, Presentation
08:00	WS 3: Interactive input on Water Management and Waste Management Input on Tools and Efficiency Guidelines. Cleaner Production, Strategies. Company specific solutions - Christian Angerbauer, Thomas Dielacher.
08:15	Task #1 > (1.5 Mini case studies tasks.doc) : <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Introduction to the basic objectives of the task and principles of it holding. Breakup of the training participants for two working groups. Start on the task 1 – “physic-chemical waste water treatment”. ▪ As a result of working on the task, each group expressed their vision for the Strategies for CP-Options, and possible approaches to solving this problem. Short discussion and analysis of chosen approach in each group (Natalia Voloshyn, Matthias Kolck, Orest Kiyko). Summarizing the results of the lesson from coaches (Thomas Dielacher) – “Right strategy is search for the source of waste and ways to minimize their formation”.
08:45	Start of discussions of preliminary results reality check at the company Mebli-Styl > (RERAM_photo_exchange) : Main remarks on the organization of workshops and equipment: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Christian Angerbauer, Thomas Dielacher : <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Remarks on outdoor lighting (must be motion sensor, time timer etc.); - “Single” windows in the office (requires additional air gap between the window glass); - No space between the radiator and window frame (min 150 mm); - Not right arranged placement of stacks at atmospheric drying area which does not allow implement natural lighting zones; - Large heat loss through the fences of the drying chamber, in particular through the door; - It is forbidden to keep glue containers directly into working area, which is also indicated on the package, also given material might be replaced by more environmentally friendly; - In production departments artificial and natural light works (it should be adjusted); - Positive aspect is a system of workplace organization; - Do not solved the problem of chipboard waste incineration;

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Company do not has any system of heat, or and exhaust air recovery, etc. ▪ Orest Kiyko : <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Should take into account that data is of 2012. This year's data is not adequate for comparison because of instability Ukrainian currency; - Might be better to use longitudinal-transverse scheme of lumber cutting. Which theoretically allows to save about 4-5% of the material. ▪ Vadim Iatchevici: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - There is no filter for exhaust gas after the boiler. ▪ Mamuka Khoshtaria: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No separation of lumber for tangential and radial direction; - The positive in using of “adhesive cans” at the bonding department; - It is inappropriate to use compressed air at the cutting workshop (long-run and large losses); - No visual warnings concerning the peril of machines, etc.
10:45	Coffee break
11:00	<p>Input on Water and Waste Management - Thomas Dielacher, Christian Angerbauer > (3.1 Watermanagement.ppt, 3.2 Wastemanagement.ppt)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Detailed explanation of the principles of work organization during reality check activity at the enterprises; ▪ Clarification as to use materials (presentation, reference books, practical tasks) at work .
12:15	<p>Conclusions and Next Steps – Uwe Kies, Roland Oberwimmer, Orest Kiyko</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Uwe Kies summarizes the outcomes of the training week. ▪ Orest Kiyko stressed following important term points in regard to selfassessment of wood-working enterprises: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - All questionnaires must be received by end of November; - All information must be strictly confidential and we cannot give anyone else only within the project. ▪ Roland Oberwimmer: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - All materials on the first TTT-WS will be available on DropBox; - Proposed and agreed date and place for the second TTT-WS 9-13 of February 2014 in Vienna-Graz (5 days) with 15-20 participants; - Next steps for Partners and HCS.
12:55	Closure and End of Training Week.

Annex 4.2.2 Impressions of the Lviv training workshops

Photo credits: FORZA NGO, UNFU

Annex 4.2.3 Impressions of Excursions and Reality Check

Photo credits: FORZA NGO, UNFU

Annex 4.2.4 Impressions of side events

Photo credits: FORZA NGO, UNFU

TRAINING MANUAL 1

Cleaner Production

Manual: Cleaner Production
First Edition, 2014

This training manual is developed by Holzcluster Steiermark for the RERAM Project. The content in this material is adopted from the ECOPROFIT Approach which originated in Austria.

This manual will be distributed free of charge to the participating trainers of the RERAM Project.

RERAM : Bridging Gaps in Research 2 Innovation in Resource Efficiency and Raw Materials

Key facts

RERAM is an international cooperation project funded by the Seventh Framework Programme of the European Commission in the field of climate protection, resource efficiency and raw materials. It is one of the few FP7-INCO projects addressing the forest-based sector (forestry, woodworking, furniture, paper, bioenergy).

The main objective is to reinforce cooperation and coordination of research and technological innovation between the EU and countries of the European Neighbourhood Policy programme especially in Eastern Europe.

RERAM raises awareness on the benefits of resource efficiency and demonstrates technical and organisational solutions for companies. With instructive enterprise checks, trainings, coaching and a broad dissemination, the project targets entrepreneurs and intermediaries to propose pathbreaking new pilot projects.

To valorise synergies and enhance the outreach in the region, the project links to various actors and on-going initiatives. Strengthening domestic potentials of woodworking SMEs, RERAM contributes to sustainable growth, vital employment and climate change adaptation in the forest-based sector of the ENP region.

Resource Efficiency and Raw Material Use of
Woodworking Industries in Eastern Europe
www.reram.eu

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1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Purpose of the ECOPROFIT Dossier "Strategies to Avoid Waste and Emissions"?

After having worked through this brochure you should be able to

**Aim of the
brochure**

- distinguish between the symptom and source of a problem of waste,
- realise the economic benefit of avoidance of waste and emissions,
- categorise the waste and emissions of your company,
- determine the factors that influence certain avoidance and reduction, and
- work out systematic solutions to the problems by means of the worksheets.

In order to achieve this we will introduce the following concepts to you:

- Definitions (waste, emissions, ...)
- Comparison of traditional waste management and a more holistic approach
- Connection between raw material, production process and waste/emission
- Factors that influence the generation of waste (Where can I start?)
- Recording of data as a basis of avoidance of waste/emissions
- Categorisation of waste and emissions and appropriate strategies of avoidance.

**Ways of
procedural steps**

Take your time (2-3 hours) to study the introduction and to think about the possible effects and consequences this process could have for your company. The time required for data collection - the most important basis for the identification of waste and emission figures - depends on the specific situation of your company, and may sometimes be rather long. In big companies, a lot of data may already be available and electronically retrievable by simply pressing some keys.

2. INFORMATION

2.1. Purpose of the ECOPROFIT Dossier "Strategies to Avoid Waste and Emissions"?

ECOPROFIT aims at an overall corporate environmental protection concept

ECOPROFIT - short for Ecological Project for Integrated Environmental Technology - is a project aimed at economic strengthening of enterprises by preventive environmental protection; at the same time it strives toward a contribution to improve the environmental standing of a region. ECOPROFIT is designed in such a way that - based on environmental problems - production processes and other activities are assessed and checked as to their utilisation of material and energy in order to trigger in-house innovations which bring both the company and the region closer to sustainable economic development. Against this background, products, technologies and material used are critically assessed in order to avoid emissions and waste and/or to ensure utilisation of the waste that cannot be avoided. ECOPROFIT is therefore not a solution for isolated individual problems but rather a tool for an overall corporate concept.

The term "eco" refers to three purposes:

What does ECOPROFIT mean?

- ecological benefit,
- economic benefit and
- in accordance with the original Greek term *oikos* (oikos, "the house, household") it underlines that a company-specific solution is to be found for your company (your house).

Help for self-help

The basic principle applies that nobody knows your company better than you and that you have important and valuable expert knowledge. ECOPROFIT will be most successful if you fully support it and encourage it. External know-how and knowledge can and should only be used for providing ideas. So ECOPROFIT means therefore first and foremost "self for self-help".

You can use the operational analysis with a view to waste and emission avoidance that is established in the framework of an ECOPROFIT project for fivefold assessment:

Evaluation of the operational analysis as ...		Evaluation for ...
Progress report, eco-controlling	⇒	management
waste management concept	⇒	authority, company
Ecological / economic analysis of weak points	⇒	staff / management
ECO audit	⇒	business partners / customers
Environmental report	⇒	the public

2.2. What are waste and emissions?

According to the definition Austrian Waste Management Act, waste includes

movable items which the owners or possessors have disposed of or want to dispose of, or that are to be recorded and handled as waste in the public interest.

Most probably, this definition is hardly applicable for operational waste management with a view to avoidance of waste. Another, better definition is: Waste and emissions are raw and process materials that have been purchased - usually at a high price - and cannot be made into sellable products or raw materials for another production process. This includes all solid, liquid and gaseous substances emitted into the air, water or soil, as well as noise and waste heat. The production process also includes other activities which are usually overlooked, such as maintenance, service and office cleaning.

Avoiding waste and emissions means ...

Avoiding waste and emissions ultimately means improving the efficiency of used materials and energies (increase of eco-efficiency) until - and that being the ideal scenario - a waste and emission-free process has been found through 100% utilisation of materials and energies.

... increasing the eco-efficiency of your company

Waste avoidance is therefore not only an environmental concern of the company but rather a managerial programme geared at enhanced utilisation of materials.

... utilising business advantages

The treatment, handling and disposal of waste and emissions may be expensive, but the costs incurred by the loss of raw materials that have been turned into waste are usually far higher.

... saving raw material costs

The worksheets in this dossier help you check this statement for your own company.

Example: Repainting a damaged car can be a highly material-intensive process. Traditional, solvent-containing enamel with approx. 60% solid matter and uneconomical spray application by means of a cup gun that is poorly adjusted and badly handled by the painter requires approx. 10 kg of raw material for an enamel film of 1 kg on the car.

By changing to an enamel with a higher solids content, use of an HVLP spray gun, a dosing unit for application and more thorough gun cleaning - i.e. combination of the best technologies available on the market - only slightly more than 2 kg of raw material are needed for the same enamel film of 1 kg on the work piece (see Fig. below). With disposal costs of approx. EUR 60.00/kg and purchasing costs of approx. EUR 900.00/kg this would mean considerable savings that must be set off against the investment cost.

2.3. What does production-integrated environmental protection mean?

So far, traditional environmental technology has mostly been implemented for further treatment or handling of waste and emissions that have already been created (examples: air filter technology, water purification, sludge processing, refuse incineration, etc.); an approach that is called end-of-pipe technology as it sets in at the end of a process. The main characteristics of the end-of-pipe technology are increased operational costs and a shift of problems from one stage to another (example: sludge production from water purification; production of gypsum from flue gas, ...).

Environmental protection must not be allowed to mean a mere shift of problems

Production-integrated - or preventive - environmental protection on the other hand aims at reducing the amount and danger of waste and emissions and - as a consequence - also the costs. Compared to the disposal of waste by third companies and to end-of-pipe technologies preventive environmental action offers several advantages:

Production-integrated environmental protection yields many advantages

- Avoidance in the sense of using smaller quantities of materials and energies has, in general, the potential for economic solutions
- Avoidance of waste and emissions usually triggers an innovative process in the company because of the intensive concentration on production processes
- Responsibility can be assumed for the entire process; risks regarding environmental liability and disposal are reduced to a minimum
- Avoidance of waste and emissions means moving towards sustainable economic development

In traditional waste management the question is:

- What is to be done with the waste and emissions created?

Preventive, integrated environmental protection on the other hand asks:

- Where do waste and emissions in my company come from?
- Why have they become waste in the first place?

The decisive difference between the two approaches is that the first simply treats the symptom while the second tries to identify the problem at the root.

from symptom to source

Example: A copper processing company produces metal-containing sludge in its waste water treatment plant. Given the high dumping costs the company is looking for a possible use of the sludge, which is, however, difficult given its high iron content.

Further investigation has shown that the amount of iron worth mentioning is only added in form of ferric chloride in the waste water treatment plant (as a typical flocculant). So the company realised that they do not so much have a sludge but rather a waste water problem.

An analysis of the main sources of waste water revealed that an excessive amount of solution of copper electrolytes is used at two stages of the production process which afterwards enters the waste water. The sludge/waste water problem has therefore become a process problem. Relatively simple organisational and technological measures helped to reduce raw material consumption at these points which in turn led to a more than 50% reduction of sludge.

A typical feature of production-integrated environmental protection is the approach of viewing the business as an integrated whole. This point of view means that raw material, energy, product, solid waste and emissions to water and air are tightly interconnected in the production process - regardless of the legal distinction between air, water and soil.

In the following table, the differences between end-of-pipe technology and integrated environmental protection are summarised.

End-of-pipe environmental technology	Integrated environmental protection
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ What do I do with waste and emissions? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Where do waste and emissions come from?
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ ... is re-active 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ is pro-active
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ ... usually causes higher costs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ ... can reduce costs
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Waste and emissions are limited by filters and processing systems End-of-pipe solution Repair technology Emission retention 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Waste and emissions are avoided at their source; processes and materials with risk/danger potential are avoided
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Environmental protection comes in only when the development of products and processes is completed 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Environmental protection is a partial aspect of product and process development
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Technological solutions for environmental problems 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Environmental problems are dealt with at all levels/in all areas

End-of-pipe environmental technology	Integrated environmental protection
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Environmental protection is the responsibility of the experts in charge 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Environmental protection concerns everybody
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ... is purchased from external sources 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ... is a company-specific innovation
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ... increases the consumption of operating means and energy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ... reduces the consumption of operating means and energy
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ... increases complexity and risk 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ... reduces risks and makes it easier to see the big picture
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Environmental protection is only a matter of fulfilling legal regulations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Environmental protection is an ongoing challenge
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ... was the outcome of the paradigm of production at a time when there were no environmental problems 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ... is the approach toward production technology in the spirit of sustainable development

Hereinafter no distinction will be made between terms such as "clean technologies", "cleaner production", "sustainable technology", "preventive environmental production". In general, they all meet the principles of integrated environmental protection explored above.

In addition to the afore-mentioned reasons for an integrated environmental protection there are also other advantages:

- Preventive action against increase in costs of waste management/ handling/processing
- Non-dependent on bottle-necks (dumping space, export permits, incineration capacities)
- Fewer problems concerning liability
- Improved image
- Fewer protests of neighbours

3.3. What factors influence the generation of waste and emissions?

If you are asked which factors influence the generation of waste and emission, you will most probably think of the technology used in your company. And technology, does play an important role, but this should not lead to the conclusion that waste avoidance would only be efficient with technological means. There are a series of other possible approaches.

Technology alone is not the only influence on the environmental standing of a company

- **Process changes** can help reducing waste and emissions to a considerable degree. The term process describes the entire work process in the company including a package of measures:
- **Careful use** of raw and process materials, which also includes organisational changes. In most cases, these measures are the best to implement and most attractive from the economic point of view. Examples: training and motivation of staff, changed sequence of handling, employment directives for materials and packing units, etc.
- **Replacement of raw and process material:** Toxic or raw and process material that is hard to recover can often be replaced by less risky materials without great investments, which ensures a major reduction of waste and emissions.
- **Change of technology:** This may reach from simple reconstructions to far-reaching process changes. This area also includes a lot of energy saving measures.

*... only then should
you ...*

Waste that cannot be avoided by taking any of the above measures should be re-fed into the production process (internal recycling, level 2), which can be handled in any of the following ways:

*consider internal
recycling*

- re-use for the same purpose,
- further use for another purpose,
- reclamation for another less important purpose, or
- material recovery of only one part of the waste material.

Only after all these steps have been taken should measures for the recovery of waste and emissions outside the company be considered (level 3). Such measures include external recycling or the refeeding of material to the biogenic cycles (e.g. composting). The recovery of operational secondary resource - such as paper, scrap, glass, compost material - and its refeeding into the economic cycle play only a limited role as far as the reduction of waste and emissions in the sense of integrated environmental protection is concerned.

*or external
recycling*

The main reason being, that no further reduction of the amount of material used in the company can be achieved that way.

Generally, it can be said that measures are more effective the more closely linked to the actual problem and the smaller the cycles are.

2.5. Avoidance is based on: data recording

*no basis of
planning
without data*

The most important requirement that has to be fulfilled in order to be able to find measures for the avoidance of waste is a good data basis. You should compile a list of the most important material flows.

Three questions are particularly intriguing as far as data collection is concerned:

- What data do I need?
- Where do I get my data from?
- What sources of pertinent information are there in my company?

Start by clarifying in which areas of your company you would like to record data; as the type of data required will depend on these areas. Taking the entire company into consideration would be the ideal solution, but perhaps you would want to exclude some partial areas.

Typical areas could be:

*How is the
balance area
defined?*

*Mass and
energy are
maintained*

By determining the areas of your company you also define the balance area. According to the principles of maintaining mass and energy every material entering a certain balance area has to leave this area again afterwards. Exception: the material is saved/stored or converted.

This means that everything that you dispose of as waste was once in your "shopping basket".

In a manufacturing enterprise, all materials and energies can be observed at three stages:

- when they enter the balance area, i.e. when being purchased
- when they leave the balance area, i.e. as product, emission, waste or thermal discharge
- when they are used according to specification; i.e. at the machine, plant

For reasons of the afore-mentioned principles of maintenance, the quantities would have to be the same at all three stages. BUT... that is all mere theory. Usually you will find that such congruence can be verified only in a few cases.

In addition to that, the following question arises: **Does the identified data correspond to reality?**

One is inclined to disregard this question as being unimportant. However, there have already been cases where operational data has been used without verification and lead to problems. The amounts recorded in book-keeping (purchasing), for example, do not necessarily have to correspond to the actual consumptio

In most areas, various documents are available displaying different qualities:

How can I record and verify my data?

Entry:

- documents for book-keeping and cost accounting,
- waybills,
- information of suppliers concerning formulae,
- in-house data identification concerning packaging
- ...

Exit:

- product lists and formulae,
- records of waste and emissions, waybills
- settlement of accounts with disposal companies,
- information of the waste water association
- ...

Use:

- cost centre accounting
- measurements at plants and machines
- information from staff concerning operating hours and change intervals
- bills of materials
- formulae
- apparatus specifications
- rating plates

As can be easily seen the data is in no specific area complete. Very often at the incoming stage, there is no data about packaging units available. In other cases it is impossible to conclude the chemical composition from the designation (e.g. cleaning agent). At the outgoing stage, there is often a lack of information about volatile material (evaporated solvents, discharged heat) and very often also about compositions or formulae.

*What should
you know after
the recording
of data?*

When the data recording is completed, you should be able to answer the following questions:

- How much raw and process materials and energy is used?
- How big are waste and emission flows?
- From which process steps do they originate?
- Which waste is hazardous / requires monitoring, and why is it hazardous?
- Which part of raw or process material becomes waste?
- Which part of raw or process material is lost as volatile emission?
- Which costs are created by the disposal of waste and the loss of purchased raw material?

But: that's a long way to go, and perhaps you have only just begun your walk.

2.6. How can waste be categorised according to its type of creation?

There are several reasons why raw materials can become waste and emissions. Depending on these reasons, waste and emissions can be identified according to categories. The table on the next page shows 11 categories. Depending on the category of waste and emissions, different strategies of avoidance and reduction can be applied. The listed avoidance strategies should serve as examples for the typical type of measure that should be taken for the respective waste category.

K*	WASTE CATEGORY	EXAMPLES	TYPICAL AVOIDANCE STRATEGIES
A	Unreacted or unused raw materials	sheet clippings, paper clippings, varnish waste, colouring substances in the waste water of textile factories	technological changes, automation, careful use, training of staff, change of raw material, better stock keeping,....
B	Impurities / side components of raw materials	Ash from fuels, fat and oil on sheets/plates, shells/hulls/peels and stones/kernels in fruit processing	choosing other raw materials, looking for possible recycling
C	Unwanted side products	gypsum from flue-gas scrubbing, sludge from waste water treatment plants	further use in the form of a new product, technological improvements, change of processes
D	Used up process materials	oils, solvents, brushes, catalysts	internal recycling, care and cleaning measures, check of dosage
E	Substances resulting from start up or carry off	products that cannot be sold, only partially filled packaging units	better work planning, training of staff, improved technology, larger lots, internal recycling
F	Defective lots, rejected parts	unsold products	improved technology, training of staff, automation, quality assurance
G	Waste and materials from maintenance	filter paper, gear lubricants, cleaning cloths	longer lifetimes, other raw material, outsourcing of activity, maintenance measures
H	Material from handling, storage, sampling, analysis, transport	residues from laboratories or from cleaning of packaging material, rotten or damaged goods	check logistics, outsourcing of activities
I	Evaporation losses	solvent losses from open packaging, desired evaporation, e.g. when painting/cleaning	Training of staff, careful handling of other raw material
J	Substances from accidents and leakages	oil binding agents, raw material or products soiled by wrong handling, heat (leakage) losses	quality assurance, better maintenance, automation, training
K	Packaging material	corrugated paperboard, films, pallets, ...	procurement guidelines, reusable/returnable packaging, recycling/recovery

K* = key

2.7. Systematic approach to avoid waste and emissions

Which mass flows are of particular importance in the company?

In order to be able to work out a systematic avoidance of waste and emissions, you should be familiar with the most important mass flows of your company. Important can have the following meanings in this respect:

- important because of legal provisions
- important because of large amounts
- important because of high costs
- important because of (eco)toxicological effects

A logical period would, for example, be one calendar year. The following worksheets that you will find in the Environmental Report Template help you with this identification:

Worksheet 3.1: The most important raw and process materials including major toxicological raw and process materials

How high is the proportion of raw and process materials that actually becomes part of the product?

Enter your most important raw and process material and substances that you consider to be toxicological, i.e. hazardous for environment and/or people. This applies mainly to those substances that are not the most important ones in your company but could still present a risk despite their small quantities. Example: certain cleaning agents or solvents used in small quantities. In addition to the quantity, the specific and the overall costs are as material as the intended purpose. Try to determine which proportion of the raw and process material becomes part of the product. Depending on the material this may be anything from 0 to 100 %. If you have no detailed measuring data or records available, start from a logical estimation. Please do not forget air, a component, which is often overlooked.

Worksheet 3.2.1: The most important products/services

What do you produce?

Enter the most important products and/or services. If the unit of measurement does not indicate the mass, it could still be useful to indicate the amount in kg if possible (convert if necessary).

Worksheet 3.2.2: The most important waste

What is the waste quantity?

Enter the most important waste streams on this worksheet. Categorisation refers to the keys already discussed. In addition to the amount of waste you will also be asked for your specific purchasing and disposal costs - state them in money unit per quantitative unit. The entire expenditure results from the specific costs multiplied by the amount.

Worksheet 3.2.3: The most important air emissions

Enter the most important processes with air emissions on this worksheet. Please mention any treatment or conditioning measures, the emitted pollutants and limits that you have to fulfil for these pollutants. Please check the limits according to local law and/or the limits written down in your permit.

Waste air must also be considered

Worksheet 3.4: Water – waste water

Enter the most important aspects of your water management on this worksheet. Start with the source of your water input and the annual consumption. Please specify any treatment of the water, where it is used and the cost.

What is water quantity you use?

In addition please make a detailed inventory of the most important water streams within the company including information about related amount of waste water, if the waste water will be treated and information about major ingredients. Please check the limits for these according to local law and/or the limits written down in your permit.

Once you have recorded the most important data, you can start to work out avoidance and reduction measures for individual types of waste and emissions and/or other problem areas. Below you will find a systematic overview of the main approaches (partly with examples). Simply check the measures suitable for your case in the tables on the respective worksheets.

Working out avoidance measures

In many cases, the avoidance strategy cannot not be allocated directly to one but to several aspects (but this will cause no problems later on).

Below there is a list of measures that can be used to avoid waste and emissions. The examples given have all been taken from actual situations and are listed for the purpose of illustration. As mentioned above, one example may serve as an illustration of various categories. Technological changes, for example, can be linked to a change of raw materials and staff training.

Possibilities of waste avoidance

Product change

Changing a product is an important strategy but often very difficult to implement in a company. Most often the dependence on customer needs/demands is quoted as a typical stumbling block. Product changes can include the following:

- **Replacing the product**

Example: A utility enterprise offers the insulation of buildings instead of a certain energy amount; solar cells instead of batteries in pocket calculators; energy-saving light bulbs.

- **Increasing its durability**

Example: Accumulators instead of batteries, improved durability through better corrosion protection

- **Change of materials**

Example: Substitutes for CFC as refrigerants

- **Change for product design**

Example: Design of furniture with a view to creating a minimum of waste pcs.; modular design makes repairs easier

- **Use of recycled material**

Example: Leather fibre remainders as a filling material for leather production; recycling plastics granules for the production of bumpers

- **Avoidance of critical components**

Example: Asbestos as thermal insulation in irons

- **Better possibilities to return used products**

Example: The electronic part of the energy-saving lamp remains, only the tube is replaced; modular design makes dismantling of parts and collection of used products easier

Replacement / change of raw and process materials

Raw and process materials can be replaced and/or changed in many ways; there is a separate worksheet specifically for these measures. Some concrete suggestions are listed below:

- **Replacement of organic solvents by aqueous solvents**

Example: Water-based enamels, aqueous-alkaline cleaning baths for metal degreasing

- **Substitution of halogenated solvents**

Example: Substitution of CFC in cleaning plants, in the production of insulating material and cooling plants; halogen-free hydrocarbon solvents instead of perchloroethylene (Per) for dry-cleaning

- **Replacement of petrochemical products by biochemical ones**

Example: Cleaning agents of a soy or rape basis, natural dyes instead of paints on petrochemical basis, vegetable lubricants

- **Choice of cleaner raw materials**

Example: Fuels with minimal sulphur content (natural gas instead of coal), minerals with less foreign material; use of neatly separated corrugated cardboard in the packaging industry; use of de-ionised water for the preparation of process solutions

- **Use of waste as raw material**

Example: Use of fibre sludge from the pulp and brick industry, products from recycled material (glass, paper, ...)

- **Use of biologically degradable substances**

Example: Biologically degradable washing-active substances

- **Reduction of the number of components**

Example: Limitation of plastics used in cars; use of unified screws for furniture assembly

- **Use of other energy carriers**

Example: Natural gas or renewable sources of energy (solar energy, hydropower, biomass) instead of coal or petrol

- **Use of substances without heavy metals**

Example: Substances without heavy metals in paints and enamels (esp. lead- and cadmium free)

- **General: Use of less ecologically critical substances**

Example: Zinc-coating without cyanide, chromatising on basis of chromium (III) instead of chromium (VI)

Technological changes

A number of measures can be taken in the field of technology. Possible modifications range from relatively simple reconstructions to major process changes. Often, these strategies are coupled to a careful handling of raw materials or the choice of modified raw materials. Given the various possible approaches, there is a separate worksheet available for technological changes. Below are some concrete examples:

▪ **Substitution of thermal and chemical processes through mechanical alternatives**

Example: Cleaning of surfaces by means of brushes or ultrasound instead of chemical cleaning with acid or alkaline solutions; engraving instead of chemical etching

▪ **Use of counterflow processes instead of single-way processes**

Example: Counterflow cascades for rinsing processes; counterflow design for drying installations; heat integration of processes of different temperatures; two-phase stripping of goods supports

▪ **Separation of waste and waste water instead of mixing**

Example: Separation of waste water flows makes the electrolytic recovery of metals possible; separate waste collection facilitates internal or external recycling

▪ **Improvement of process conditions**

Example: Change of pressure and temperature to increase exploitation; selection of suitable catalysts

▪ **Increase of energy effectiveness, waste heat use**

Energy can be more effectively used through various measures:

Measures	Examples
Reduction of heat losses	Insulation of the heat source and/or heat consumer
Reduction of distribution losses	Insulation of lines
Heat recovery	Warming of air with hot kiln flue-gases; utilisation of flash vapour
Load management	Disconnection of individual systems such as hall suction systems etc, at peak times
Combined heat & power	Own gas-driven combined heat-and-power system for heat, electricity and if required cold
Switching light and heating off when not required	... for example with movement sensors
Energy-efficient drives with speed control	for pumps, conveyor systems, ventilation systems, flue-gas fans

- **Enclosure of plants (air)**

Example: Enclosure of cleaning installations working with chlorinated hydrocarbons (required according to CHC directive)

- **Re-use, use for multiple purposes (water)**

Example: Change of water cycle so that the rinsing water of an acid caustic bath can also be used as rinsing water of the previous alkaline degreasing bath; rinsing water cycle with ion-exchanger system

- **Prolongation of useful life of chemicals / substances**

Example: Preparation of cooling lubricant emulsions by means of ultrafiltration, pH and bacteria control, use of extra-fine oil filters in the automobile industry

- **Reduction of foreign matter drag-in**

Example: Covering process baths, cleanliness in the storage areas

Careful operating method

As already described above, this group of measures is one of the most effective approaches; the investment expenditure is usually low while saving potential is high. In addition to careful handling of raw and process materials, organisational measures are also included in the strategy package.

- **Careful operating mode; the following measures can be taken:**

Measures	Examples
Change of dosage / concentration	Reduction of temperature of degreasing baths; change of pH values of solutions; testing whether lower chemical concentrations than those indicated by the manufacturer would be possible (manufacturers often indicate concentrations that are too high, to be on the safe side); installation of a rinsing water control unit
Increasing rate of process utilisation	Fill batch drier completely; create puffers in order to operate continuous flow systems at full load (avoidance of unnecessary partial load losses); switching machines and devices off that are not needed at the moment
Putting cleaning and maintenance intervals into question	Reduction of cleaning steps at batch-wise yoghurt production; check oil change with regard to time, operating hours and quality assurance
Avoiding evaporation losses and leakage	Removal from barrels by means of hand pumps (appropriate sealing required)

Measures	Examples
Improvement of purchasing, stock keeping and delivery	Refuse to accept damaged barrels; do not accept any unnecessary enamel samples; internal transport in closed systems (lines)
Material flow tracking	A water balance shows the biggest consumers and leakages in the company and suggests possible savings

▪ **Improved waste logistics**

Improved waste logistics / separation of waste can have the following advantages:

- It makes the closing of cycles possible,
- can make recovery possible,
- can minimise the amount of hazardous waste,
- can minimise disposal costs,
- can minimise cleaning expenditure.

Example: newly design waste collection points with colour coding; waste separation as early as at the work place

▪ **Better information**

- Change of attitude/consciousness
- Trainings
- Work instructions, waste-avoiding operating instructions
- Transparency of costs
- Including consumption, loss and emission figures in the existing documents
- Definition of responsibilities
- Cooperation with accounting

Example: Staff trainings, information on the "green board", appointment of waste management officers in the individual departments, idea competitions, creation of environment teams, IT presentation of material utilisation

▪ **Standardisation / automation**

Example: Manual removal of racks in a galvanic application was automated in order to minimise carry-over losses; specification of cleaning intervals; specification of paints and tools to be used

▪ **Changes in procurement**

Example: Reduction of the many different cleaning agents to a number of three

Internal closing of loops

Internal closing of loops includes further measures that can be subdivided as follows:

- **Re-use: using a substance or product for the same purpose as before**

Example: Recovery of solvents for the same application, reusable packaging, washing of cleaning cloths; electrolytic or chemical recycling of chemical etching/pickling solutions

- **Further use: using a material or article for another purpose**

Example: Using the solvent acetone only for cleaning purposes, use of enamel remainders for enamelling parts that cannot be seen (e.g. underbody)

- **Reclamation (down-cycling): using a material for another, usually inferior, purpose**

Example: Plastic or paper waste as filling material for packaging

- **Resource recovery: recovery and use of only part of the waste material**

Example: Silver recovery from photo chemicals

External recycling

The general subdivision of internal recycling also applies for external recycling. For the reasons mentioned above, an internal closing of loops should be preferred. It is also important to know whether it is true recycling or down-cycling, which only means that the time of dumping is shifted.

Example: Aluminium; glass, metal recovery from waste water sludge; but also plastics as noise protection walls and park benches

We can also distinguish between

- **Re-use of entire structures**

Example: Packaging material as packaging material, pallets as pallets

- **Use of materials**

Example: Waste paper, scrap as raw material for production

▪ Use of energy content

Example: Pallet used as heating material

In addition to the actual recycling of material, external recycling may also include the feeding of waste into biogenic cycles. Example: Composting of bottle labels from milk and beer bottle cleaning

Change of the course of manufacture / leaving one process step out

In some areas, the justified question arises whether a change of the course of manufacture would not mean that an entire process step can be left out, so that no waste is created in the first place.

Example: No intermediate greasing of metal sheets; no chromating of metal parts which are afterwards coating with a corrosion-proof coating anyway, no base coat; no unnecessary drying steps

Reusable packaging

As far as packaging is concerned, there are several possible approaches for the avoidance of waste consisting of the measures discussed above.

Example: Use of 1000 l reusable grid boxes instead of 70 l disposable packaging material; use of compostable packaging and/or filling material (on pulp/paper or vegetable starch basis); packing furniture in cloth; packaging size adjusted to purpose (not too small and not too big); emptying packaging entirely.

You have now heard or read some incentives to avoid waste and should have come up with a lot of ideas and strategies for your company. Please write them down in a few words and carry out a first, simple evaluation of your ideas and strategies with the help of the worksheets enclosed. The evaluation (simple 3-step evaluation) should provide you with information concerning the importance and the presumable improvement potential of the individual measures in your company.

An exact evaluation of quantitative and cost reduction as well as a possible implementation will only be possible after a comprehensive input-output-balance and/or material flow analysis. Please refer to dossier 4 of this series.

In the Appendix you will find a list of worksheets on the topic of waste avoidance which may provide you with some arguments for discussions of this topic.

3. OUR EXAMPLE - YOUR EXAMPLE: FROM THEORY TO PRACTICE

The worksheets of the Environmental Report Template for

- **data collection (no. 3.1, 3.2.1, 3.2.2, 3.2.3, 3.4)**

have been filled in as an example of our fictitious brewery. Use the worksheets to help you with the evaluation and assessment of your company or adjust the sheets to your specific requirements. In the Appendix you will find the respective sheets.

Please note our hints in chapter 2!

You should now

- know the most important material flows in your company (waste, raw and process materials)
- have an overview of the costs of raw material losses
- know strategies for the avoidance and reduction of waste and emissions in your company, even if the exact feasibility study has yet to be made
- know possible (ways of) approaches to improve the efficiency of your processes.

This knowledge may be very useful in future. We have provided you with a sound basis for arguments concerning the actual cost situation. You will be able to prepare documents for your management in such a way that more favourable amortisation times are shown for necessary investments.

4. APPENDIX

Worksheets from Environmental Report:

Worksheet 3.1: The most important raw and process materials including major toxicological raw and process materials

Worksheet 3.2.1: The most important products/services

Worksheet 3.2.2: The most important waste

Worksheet 3.2.3: The most important air emissions

Worksheet 3.4: Water – waste water

3.1 Input

Worksheet 3.1

The most important raw and process materials including major toxicological raw and process materials

20 most important raw and auxiliary material in terms of quantity + 20 most important raw and auxiliary material in terms of cost
+ 20 most important raw and auxiliary material in terms of toxicity

No.	Material	Quantity per annum (approx)	Unit	Specific cost (EUR)	Approx. Total cost (EUR)	Purpose	% going into the product
1							
2							
3							
4							
5							
6							
7							
8							
9							
10							
11							
12							
13							
14							
15							
16							
17							
18							
19							
20							

3.2 Output

Worksheet 3.2.1

The most important products and services

No.	Product	Quantity per annum	Unit	Sales (EUR)
1				
2				
3				
4				
5				
6				
7				
8				
9				
10				
11				
12				
13				
14				
15				
16				
17				
18				
19				
20				

Worksheet 3.2.2
The most important waste

Non hazardous waste:

Description/definition of waste	Where does the waste arise?	Waste quantity /year [kg]	Who collects the waste? (private disposal company, municipality)	Is there waste treatment in the company? If so, please describe it	Interval of waste collection	Disposal costs/year Revenue (-) (EUR)

Hazardous waste:

Description/definition of waste	Where does the waste arise?	Waste quantity /year [kg]	Who collects the waste? (private disposal company, municipality)	Is there waste treatment in the company? If so, please describe it	Interval of waste collection	Disposal costs/year Revenue (-) (EUR)

3.4 Water – waste water

Worksheet 3.4

Water – waste water: annual consumption and structure

Data concerning the annual consumption of water, water sources (communal water, water from a well) and water treatment

Water source	Annual water consumption [m ³]	Treatment	Company area	Cost (EUR)

Inventory following the separated use of water in the company

Process or production/auxiliary plant with water consumption	Company area	Annual water consumption [m ³]	Annual waste water amount [m ³]	ETP [1] YES/NO	Ingredients (before discharge)	Limits/ Thresholds for [2]

[1] Effluent Treatment Plant

[2] according to local law

Description of the waste water treatment (e.g. direct discharge, neutralization) concerning the single processes and the waste water analyses which have been carried out:

Disclaimer:

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TRAINING MANUAL 2

Material Flow Analysis

Manual: Material Flow Analysis
First Edition, 2014

This training manual is developed by Holzcluster Steiermark for the RERAM Project. The content in this material is adopted from the ECOPROFIT Approach which originated in Austria.

This manual will be distributed free of charge to the participating trainers of the RERAM Project.

RERAM : Bridging Gaps in Research 2 Innovation in Resource Efficiency and Raw Materials

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RERAM raises awareness on the benefits of resource efficiency and demonstrates technical and organisational solutions for companies. With instructive enterprise checks, trainings, coaching and a broad dissemination, the project targets entrepreneurs and intermediaries to propose pathbreaking new pilot projects.

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Resource Efficiency and Raw Material Use of
Woodworking Industries in Eastern Europe
www.reram.eu

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1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. What are the goals of the ECOPROFIT dossier „material flow analysis“?

After working through this dossier you will be able to illustrate a particular material flow in your company. You will be able to:

- follow the route of raw material through the company
- trace back waste to its origin
- prepare ready-to-use data
- discover weak spots in the proceedings and
- establish meaningful priorities for waste and emissions avoidance measures.

Thus it will be easy for you to complete the mandatory documentation of industrial waste and to develop a waste management concept. This method can also be applied to the analysis of energy consumption, waste water accumulation as well as to the source of gaseous emissions. Moreover you will recognize actual weak spots in the use of materials and will define measures for its avoidance.

You should spend a total of four hours familiarizing yourself with this ECOPROFIT dossier: You will need about an hour to study the introduction and a further hour to work out the practice examples. You should then reserve two hours to transfer your knowledge, which is ready for use in your company.

***How do we use
this dossier***

2. INFORMATION

2.1. What is „material flow analysis“?

The so-called „material flow analysis“ is a systematic approach

- to obtain an overview of the use of material in a company;
- to document the site, amount and causes of wastes and emissions (noise and air pollution, waste water, etc.);
- to provide the basis for the evaluation and estimation of future development;
- to define measures for improvement.

Industrial waste and emission problems originate where materials in the production are used, manufactured or transformed. To strategically solve the environmental problems of a company therefore it is of primary importance to document a model of the material flows; to understand source, amount and cause of wastes and emissions; to become better acquainted with substances you work with; to determine the current value of these substances and to accurately estimate possible future developments in time. An information system has to be created to make it possible for the management to comprehend, to influence and to optimize the efficiency of the use of the material flow in the company.

„A material flow analysis system takes stock of the route of a chemical element, a compound or of a material in its natural cycle and/or through an economic cycle. A material flow analysis is normally based on the physical principle of balance.“
(Enquete commission „protection of mankind and the environment“ of the German Lower House of Parliament, 1993)

One can therefore compare material flow analysis with a map. Instead of cities this company „map“ shows steps in the production, and instead of streets and rivers the material flows within the company are shown.

And just as with a map, the material flow´s clear graphic presentation is an important criterion. Therefore one attempts to graphically prepare the information gained from the material flow analysis on origin, use and remains of raw, auxiliary and industrial materials so that it can be interpreted as fast as possible.

Different types of graphics have proved helpful:

Flow charts to show material flows and procedures

Graphics and histograms to illustrate distributions and material make-up to show x-y-graphics

sankey diagrams of to scale of material visualization flows

The presentation and evaluation of such processes are already in daily practice in paper and cellulose industry plants and in plants of the chemical or the oil industry. Make use of these instruments in your company as well!

2.2. How do we proceed with the material flow?

There are seven steps to a complete material flow:

1. Definition of the goal and of the observed parameters
 2. Boundaries of the balance space
 3. Boundaries of the balance time period
 4. Registering and naming the production steps
 5. Draft of the flow chart: material flows - qualitative
 6. Balances: material flow - quantitative
 7. Interpretation and conclusions

Steps 2 - 5 are also called „system analysis“. The system analysis identifies the relevant system elements and illustrates the relationships between them.

2.2.1 Choice of the parameters:

The material flow analysis goal has to be initially defined because the requirements of the observed parameters and the scope of the study also depend on this goal. The goal of a material flow analysis can be to follow (for whatever reason: costs, risks, disposal safety, volumes) material flows, special chemical compounds or single elements of special interest through the company. The question concerning the necessary level of resolution has to be clarified at the beginning of the analysis.

Therefore a material flow analysis for the entire company will be made. This will define at the company's boundary which materials in what amounts and of what value are used within the company and which wastes and emissions (in addition to the products) leave the company. This occurs systematically within an input/output - analysis.

From stock or accounting all raw, auxiliary and industrial materials as well as the energy sources used are registered in their amounts and values. Products and emissions are handled in the same way. It is a matter of a material balance on an industrial level. Expensive and ecologically problematic materials are therefore of primary interest for a detailed analysis.

To set the priority you organize the flows in their values and toxicity according to an ABC - analysis. (See also ECOPROFIT dossier 1 .)

Tip: Take the list you have made working through ECOPROFIT dossier 1, of your 20 most expensive, the 20 most poisonous raw materials and of the 20 most important wastes. If data are missing make an estimation and collect the data later in your company. Which of these materials do you now want to study in detail? What is your most urgent problem? Organize your material flows according to value and toxicity in an ABC - analysis. Later we will examine a case study, following the route of water in a brewery. Which material in your company do you want to examine in a material flow analysis?

The material chosen:

2.2.2. The balance space

**How do we
limit the
balance
space**

The balance space can include the entire company or individual processes. Its definition is once again goal - oriented. First one examine the company as a whole. To localize exactly the possibilities of influence processes will be structured in detail.

2.2.3. The balance time period

A choice of a representative period has proved itself as the balance time period. That can be a balance year, a month, but also a charge or a production week.

Choose the balance time period!

2.2.4. Registering and naming the production steps

The process is then organized in the relevant steps which describe its structure and function and it will be shown in a flow chart. Therefore one follows already implemented activities or the machines and facilities used or cost centres. Rectangles illustrating the production steps and arrows demonstrating the material flows are used as presentational elements.

Organizing the procedures in the company

2.2.5. Draft of a flow chart

All relevant information (components, value, mass, origin of the data, ecological relevance) is assigned to the flows. All important information (such as temperature, charge, etc.) is documented as well for the individual procedure steps (or apparatus). These flow charts can be used later when drawing up the waste management concept.

Flow charts illustrate the process

2.2.6. Balances

Just as for the entire company all „production steps“, system elements, the principle of mass conservation, the balance principle has to be satisfied. When stationary condition the mass inflow must be equal to the outflow. All raw, auxiliary and industrial materials that enter an element have to leave it again as a product, waste or emission. That is why it is calculated in mass units (kg).

Pay attention to the principle of mass conservation when drawing up the balances

2.2.7. Interpretation

The flow chart is interpreted by following the material paths (an illustration of the exact place of waste origin, the connections between raw materials and wastes) and by creating indexes in the form of efficiencies (cost / use benefits) and by the levels of quality (proportion of the actual to the theoretical possible efficiency) for the entire company and for the individual production steps.

What can you derive from the balance and the flow charts?

Tip: Please refer to the ECOPROFIT dossier „Environmental Controlling“.

The comparison of information on the actual process efficiency with references will reveal weak-spots. They must be prioritized to be processed further. This will require a discussion process within the company. Periodic updating of the process data creates an instrument for technical controlling, with which the development of

the use and the whereabouts of materials can also be documented in future.

Tip: Collect information on your selected material, apparatus and problematical procedure: Does the competition use this material; how much does he need compared to you; can your supplier recommend a problem-free substitute material of equal value?

Suitable answer strategies to improve the efficiency of the material use can be:

- to deal more carefully with raw and auxiliary materials (strict adherence to formulae, complete emptying of containers, sealing leaks...)
- to substitute raw and auxiliary materials (raw materials free of formaldehyde, heavy metal, chlorine...)
- process changes (for example: automatic settings)
- product changes
- internal recycling (closed water cycles, recycling materials in the company...)
- external recycling (recycling scrap metal, composting biodegradable materials...)

2.3 Where does the necessary information come from?

First we implement our system analysis by defining the balance space, the balance time period and by identifying the relevant process steps using work sheet 1 (process steps). We then draft a flow chart of the procedure using work sheet 2 (procedure flow chart). We need the following data for the material flow analysis for the materials examined:

- **Type**
- **Amount**
- **Value**
- **Place of use and place of origin**

This data is now to be gathered in the company using work sheet 3 (detailing material paths).

The columns „number“ and „type“ characterize a material flow numerating the material flows in the flow chart and writing-in the flow number and the corresponding type in work sheet 3.

In the column „amount“ we note the amount a material is used or available; in the adjoining column „unit“ we enter the unit used for our data.

To make a balance we need the particular amounts in (kg). Therefore we have to define (or estimate) a conversion factor of

our units of amount, which can also include units of volume or number of units. These are entered in the column „factor“. We transfer the available or now calculable amount in (kg) to the column „(kg)“. When dealing with great amounts we can also use the unit (t) (tons) instead of (kg).

We record the value of the particular flow to get a picture of the material value of use, waste and product flows, using the column „value“. We obtain the value from book-keeping or from cost accounting.

Foot notes on the work sheets list several possible sources of data. To document the source of data use the column of the same name.

Information on input is found in the company accountancy concerning raw, auxiliary and industrial materials or in the department for economic use of materials under the material numbers.

Information on inner company material flows are obtained via computer (for example: production planning and control system), through oral information given by the plant manager or foreman, by the work preparation or production books. If the necessary information on amount or value cannot be obtained in this manner, one has to rely on one´s own measurements or estimation.

Generally output stream estimations are obtained from sales reports, disposal invoices and records of waste water and emission measurements.

In this manner data for the mass of a material entering the company, for its process through and whereabouts in the company´s output should be determined. The ideal situation will therefore present a consistent material balance. The input must be equal to the output. This must apply in exactly the same way to balances in detail concerning individual process steps.

2.4. The use of data sheets and computer programs

Data collection sheets, check lists and interview forms from the trade literature are a help above all in a careful documentation of the waste avoidance project and are a support when searching for potentials for emissions avoidance. However, before use they should be carefully examined and where necessary adapted to real-case applicability. The user should not be given the sheets to fill out without prior explanation.

Tip: Familiarize yourself with the data sheets in the appendix of this ECOPROFIT dossier and with the check lists on waste avoidance in ECOPROFIT dossier 1

PC and table calculation programs like MS-Excel are the standard equipment of every office today. They can be useful for data administrations, calculations and graphic evaluations and presentations.

3. OUR EXAMPLE – YOUR EXAMPLE: THE MATERIAL FLOW IN A BREWERY

A brewery is dissatisfied with the high yearly water consumption of 272.000 m³: Fresh water costs alone are 484.000.- EUR! Analyze the material flow of water. The company has the following water users:

- production (describing all processes from boiling the beer, storage, filtering up to bottling)
- their own truck wash and sanitary installations
- bottle and container cleaning
- cooling facilities

Waste water the truck wash, from the sanitary installations, from the bottle and container cleaning and from production is channelled to the company sewage treatment plant.

The following data are known: from accountancy:

- total yearly water consumption : 272.000 m³.
- fresh water costs: 484.000.- EUR,
- waste water costs: 538.000.- EUR,

after observing the entries in the relevant water accounts (the water meter is read weekly):

- 102.000 m³ are used to cool
- 42.500 m³ go into the production
- 10.000 m³ are used in the sanitary installations and in the truck wash
- the rest is used in facilities cleaning
- 25.000 m³ of production water is contained in the beer to be sold, the rest goes in wet draff, in used filter material and in traces of waste water when cleaning.

Assign the water consumption to production, cooling water, sanitary installations and cleaning; define the causes of water consumption and find suitable measures to reduce it. Try to implement a material flow analysis using the forms provided to the company.

Tip: Familiarize yourself with the company description of the brewery! Draw a flow chart for the company water supply and describe the most important process flows. Organize water consumption (in kg/kg beer to be sold) according to the other consumers: production vat, cleaning and sanitary facilities. Evaluate these calculations in a diagram!

4. APPENDIX

Worksheet 1: Process steps

Worksheet 2: Procedure flow chart

Worksheet 3: Detailing material paths

Example: Summary of material flow analysis in brewery

5. WORKSHEETS

Worksheet 1	Dossier 2	Example
Process steps		

Examined material:	water	
Person handling the case:	F.Müller	Date: 14.2.1998
Balance space:	Grünbier Brewery	Balance time period: 1997

The material will be used in the following fields:

Name of the field	Regular use (marked with a cross)	In special cases
Truck wash and sanitary installations	X	
Bottle and container cleaning	X	
Production	X	
Cooling system	X	
Sewage treatment plant	X	

Worksheet 1	Dossier 2	Action Plan
Process steps		

Examined material:

Person handling the case: **Date:**

Balance space: **Balance time period:**

The material will be used in the following fields:

Name of the field	Regular use (marked with a cross)	In special cases

Worksheet 2

Dossier 2

Example

Procedure flow chart

additional information

no

overleaf

process description

yes

no

Worksheet 2	Dossier 2	Action Plan
Procedure flow chart		

Procedure flow chart: number for

additional information	<input type="radio"/> no	<input type="radio"/> overleaf
process description	<input type="radio"/> yes	<input type="radio"/> no

Worksheet 3	Dossier 2	Example
Detailing material paths		

Examined material:	water	
Person handling the case:	F. Müller	Date: 14.2.1998
Balance space:	Grünbier Brewery	Balance time period 1997

Number acc. to the flow chart	name	amount	unit	factor ¹	kg	value	Source of data ²
I1	well water	272000	M ³	1 t/m ³		484000	Accounting
1	water for fishing	10000	M ³	1 t/m ³			Meter
2	water for cleaning	117500	M ³	1 t/m ³			Calculate
3	water for production	42500	M ³	1 t/m ³			Meter
4	water for cooling	102000	M ³	1 t/m ³			Meter
5	sewage inflow	142000	M ³	1 t/m ³			Meter
O1	waste water	244000	M ³	1 t/m ³		538000	Meter
O2	wet draff	3000	T			0	Calculate
O3	beer for sale	25000	M ³	1 t/m ³		25000000	Accounting

¹ conversion of the data unit to units of measurement (kg)

² verbal information (work preparation, foreman) computer (PPS-system)
company books, routine measurements, own measurements, estimation

Worksheet 3	Dossier 2	Action Plan
Detailing material paths		

Examined material:

Person handling the case: **Date:**

Balance space: **Balance time period**

Number acc. to the flow chart	name	amount	unit	factor ³	kg	value	Source of data ⁴

³ conversion of the data unit to units of measurement (kg)

⁴ verbal information (work preparation, foreman) computer (PPS-system)
company books, routine measurements, own measurements, estimation

Worksheet

Dossier 2

Example

The following diagram illustrates the water flow through the brewery based on 1 kg beer for sale. 10,9 kg of input are necessary to produce 1 kg of beer for sale! From these 10,9 kg, 1,7 are used directly in production, 4,1 l as cooling water, the rest 5,1 kg are used for cleaning (bottle and container cleaning, vets and pipelines, truck wash).

Distribution of water consumption in the brewery

In the broader sense 45% of the water used is for cleaning. Possible starting points toward reducing water consumption in those steps would be a study on the necessity of cleaning production facilities and tanks, and also an analysis of the frequency of truck washing. Can you use the warmed cooling water for cleaning? The waste water from the cleaning operations contributes a major part of the hydraulic load in the sewage treatment plant. You should now present the diagram to the management, if you are presenting the results of your study. Further analyses could study possibilities in closing company water cycles.

For technical controlling in the company it is recommended to introduce a cleaning water index. (defined as kg for cleaning water, sanitation, trucks per beer for sale) Its value for the current year is 5,1. Its development should be observed to make possible conclusions on how to deal with cleaning water more economically.

A potential reduction in water use can be expected, because since the cleaning processes are not automated but rather carried out manually. The cleaning process should perhaps be standardized and be supported by the automation of the whole process or of partial steps (switching on and off automatically, etc.).

Tip: Now take your selected material and analyze its flow through your company

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TRAINING MANUAL 3

Waste Management

Manual: Waste Management
First Edition, 2014

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Resource Efficiency and Raw Material Use of
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1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Purpose of the ECOPROFIT “Waste Management – Optimising Logistics”?

With the aid of this dossier from the “ECOPROFIT series” you will be able to analyse the specific waste management system of your company and improve the logistics employed with regard to non-hazardous waste, hazardous waste and waste oil. You can and should also check whether your company observes the regulations of the local authorities, its implementing ordinances, and other legislation pertaining to waste management, and if necessary initiate any corrections.

Aim of the brochure

However, please note: avoiding waste is more economical and ecological than collecting and recycling waste!

If you have analysed and, if necessary, improved your company’s specific waste management system with the aid of the worksheets in Chapters 3 and 4, you have already elaborated two major parts of your company’s waste management concept.

Why is it necessary to review waste legislation if we are only planning to improve logistics?

Legislation on waste constitutes the foundation for your company’s waste logistics system. If you are not properly informed about these regulations, you will risk building up your waste logistics system incorrectly, thus making bad investments and having to pay fines for not observing regulations.

Interplay of waste legislation and waste logistics

So, what is the whole point of analysing your waste management system and optimising logistics?

- You can be sure that all waste-related regulations are observed.
- You will be informed about developments in terms of quantity and pricing of non-hazardous waste, hazardous waste and waste oil, and can take targeted measures of avoiding and recycling this waste.
- A working waste logistics system ensures that reusable waste, but equally so hazardous waste, are properly separated and no longer end up in the expensive general waste.
- It means cutting the volume of residual waste and, in most cases, waste disposal and recycling costs, and maximising revenue.
- A working waste management system is an integral part of your company’s waste management concept and environmental protection programme.
- You will be able to motivate your colleagues because, for many people, a working system of waste separation is often the clearest example of active environmental policy.

Benefit

- You will contribute to protecting the environment and economising on resources.

Obstacles

What are the “reasons” not to improve your waste logistics?

- Costs: costs of conversion, e.g. staff, investment, training costs, etc.!
- Lethargy: why should we change our system - it works the way it is!
- Little benefit: separating waste costs more than dumping it!

But:

- Analysing the waste management & optimising logistics does “pay” - in most cases in the short term, and in all cases in the long run.
- Both aspects are also an important part of the overall environmental protection concept.

What happens once the landfills are full?

Current landfill situation

It will be necessary to build new landfills with a large volume of public and private funding and extremely long planning periods, and old landfills will need to be renovated at great expense. Just imagine the opposition if a landfill were set up nearby where you live! The landfill price will be very high in future, thus reflecting the scarcity of this commodity. Companies already cutting back on their industrial waste will thus be at an advantage in future.

1.2. How is this brochure structured?

Structure of the brochure

Chapter 1 explains the pros and cons of implementing such a project, the schedule of events and the amount of time required and briefly describes what you will find in the each of the chapters.

Chapter 2 contains the scheduling and procedure information required for project implementation.

By example of a fictitious brewery, **Chapter 3** demonstrates how the framework waste management legislation can be fulfilled, how you can present logistics for non-hazardous waste, hazardous waste and waste oil in a clear-cut manner for all affected areas of the company, and what information you will need. With the aid of worksheets, you can easily collect company details.

Again, by example of the brewery, **Chapter 4** shows what improvements can be made and how the data you have collated can be prepared in the form of presentation material for the management so as to secure approval and support for implementation of the planned measures of waste avoidance and recycling.

Schedule

1. First of all, read this brochure carefully.
2. Then study the brewery example (Chapters 3 and 4) and make notes on whatever also applies to your company.
3. Next, follow the procedure detailed under 2.1.2.:

- Discuss the project with the management and the environment task force.
- Familiarise yourself with the concepts and regulations of waste management legislation.
- Check that waste management regulations are observed and initiate any corrections that may be needed.
- Try to allocate the types of waste produced to the appropriate areas.
- Collect data on volumes of waste and costs of disposal.
- Inspect the company - together with your colleagues, identify the specific weaknesses and possible improvements in the company.
- Discuss the results in the environment task force.
- Present the results to the management.
- Implement the specific company measures.

2. INFORMATION

2.1. How to analyse the waste management system and optimise logistics

2.1.1. The problem

What is the waste situation like in many companies?

In many companies, the people in charge do not even know that there can be problems with waste, as they have little or no knowledge of the relevant waste management legislation and are not aware of the composition of their general waste. Who wants to look - let alone poke around - in waste containers? That's other people's job - is that what it's like at your company?

In many cases, no suitable container systems are used for the purpose of waste separation, and the workforces have no, inadequate or incorrect information about separating waste. This leads to an excessive amount of reusable, but also hazardous, waste in the general waste.

With regard to the landfill ordinance (following prolonged interim regulations, extremely high quality demands will be imposed on waste dumped at public and corporate landfills in future), such a situation jeopardises guaranteed disposal for the company. The company also violates existing laws.

Test yourself!

Can you answer the following questions?

Test questions on waste management legislation

What are the types of waste produced at your company?

How does your company observe the recording obligation for non-hazardous waste?

How is fine packaging fraction (from outside products or brought into the company by workers) separated at your company - how many kg did this total in 20xx?

How many kg of biological waste were collected last year and how much does recycling cost?

If you answered all four questions, you have already fulfilled some important points - congratulations. Nevertheless, we advise you to review the following items.

If you cannot answer any or some of the questions, it is high time to give your company a thorough check!

2.1.2. The solution

Analyse your waste management system and optimise the specific company logistics!

Together with the environment task force (see Vol. 1), initiate the project "Analysis of waste management - Optimisation of logistics". Use the experience gained in many areas for this project and observe the following procedure to analyse the waste management system and optimise the company's logistics:

***Procedure for
analysing waste
management***

- Discuss the project with the management and the environment task force.
- Familiarise yourself with the concepts and regulations of waste management legislation.
- Check that waste management regulations are observed and initiate any corrections.
- Try to allocate the types of waste produced to the appropriate areas.
- Collect data on volumes of waste and costs of disposal.
- Inspect the company - together with your colleagues, identify the specific weaknesses and possible improvements in the company.
- Discuss the results in the environment task force.
- Present the results to the management.
- Implement the specific company measures.

Discuss the project with the management and the environment task force!

The “Analysis of waste management - Optimisation of logistics” project should be initiated and implemented by you and the environment task force (see Vol. 1). Thus, inform the environment task force and the management and secure their support. Whether or not you carry out the surveys on your own or in a team will depend on the size of the company and the existing organisational structure of your company's waste management system.

Familiarise yourself with the concepts and regulations of waste management legislation!

If you are not yet familiar with the concepts and regulations of waste management legislation, it will be an advantage for you to study them before beginning the surveys. You will learn to use the correct terms and get a good overview of the applicable regulations (see Dossier 8 of this series).

Use the information material handed out during the “Waste management” workshop of the ECOPROFIT general programme. If you have not taken part in this general programme and you want to inform yourself about the concepts and regulations of waste management, please contact: local authorities (department of environmental protection. They will be pleased to send you the material.

Try to allocate the types of waste produced to the appropriate areas!

Before analysing waste logistics on site, go to worksheet 2 A and try to enter your company's specific types of waste in the “General waste management plan”.

This will give you an initial overview of the various areas of the company in terms of waste. Make any notes on this general plan in worksheet 2 B. Use the brewery example as a guide-line.

Enter the following details in the general “waste management” plan and the worksheet entitled “Notes on the general plan”:

- Areas of the company (e.g. production, storage, administration, central waste site, workshop, printing shop, etc.)
- Give the areas identifiers based on existing designations (e.g. production = A, storage = B, office = C, etc.)
- Now enter the following data for each area: types of waste, number of staff, evaluation of waste separation, waste officer

The things you cannot enter at this stage should be identified during inspection of the works.

**Types of waste
in various
areas of the
company**

Collect data on volumes of waste and costs of disposal!

Next, with the aid of worksheets 3 A - 3 B survey the volumes of waste actually produced at your company, prices of disposal and revenue from individual waste fractions (use Vol. 3 of this series to identify the environmental costs of company waste).

**Survey of volumes
of waste and costs
of disposal**

Recording waste-related data in worksheets 3 A - 3 B, it will also help you to identify the development of waste volumes. It is an advantage to survey data from the past two years. If these data are collected prior to inspecting the company, you will know the recycling fees, disposal costs and revenue from individual types of waste when you go on the inspection; what types of waste have been recorded so far; who is responsible for disposal; etc. If you cannot fill in the column entitled “*origin of waste*” yet, fill it in during the works inspection.

Do a works inspection - identify the specific weaknesses and possible improvements at your company!

Now inspect your company and inform all workers in the various departments about the project. Discuss the available data with the people in charge and collaborate to collect any data still needed. Include cleaning staff (also from outside firms!) in your data collection.

Works inspection

The aim of the works inspection is to identify and document the specific weaknesses of the company and to discuss possible improvements on the spot with the people involved.

Take photos of the current waste logistics system and also the composition of the general waste and use these photos or slides in your presentation to the management. This will help you get the support of the management more easily for subsequent implementation of your suggested measures.

Look in the waste containers and estimate the percentage of reusable waste in the general waste. Note whether any hazardous waste is contained. If you have a waste compressor you cannot look inside, lock it up and check the waste deposited during the course of a whole day or go to the landfill and inspect the waste dumped there. Enter the specific weaknesses of the company in worksheet 4 B.

During your works inspection, inform your colleagues about the types of waste that have to be separated by law and have them participate in drawing up specific suggestions for improvement. (Container systems, key colours for different types of waste, sites, labels and signs, decentralised collection points, adaptation of the central collection point, etc.)

As a suggestion, use the examples indicated in the “waste management” seminar of the ECOPROFIT general programme and draw up a tailor-made solution for your company. Also enter the suggested improvements in worksheet 4 B and identify the economic and ecological impact entailed by optimising your waste logistics system.

Also find out how your colleagues were informed about waste separation and consider how this information should be prepared even at this early stage. If a particular area of the company does not have a waste officer yet, ask who would be willing to take care of proper waste separation and informing colleagues when you inspect the works.

Waste officers need not be heads of departments but should be committed to environmental issues. Waste officers are important partners who will in future ensure that waste is properly separated and inform your colleagues about waste-related matters. In order to fulfil this task, waste officers need regular training.

Discuss the results in the environment task force!

Planning measures with the environment task force

Present the results of your surveys at the next meeting of the environment task force. Indicate what still needs to be done to fulfil the legal requirements and what options are available for improving your company's specific logistics system for non-hazardous waste, hazardous waste and waste oil. Next, decide in the team what options should be implemented at your company.

Next, obtain quotations for container systems, waste presses or other waste treatment equipment, installation of waste collection points, etc. and indicate the economic and ecological impact of the planned measures.

Negotiate with your disposer whether he will be general disposer, what terms will apply in future and whether he can provide container systems free of charge.

Discuss the presentation material for the management in the team. Chapter 4 suggests how to prepare the results for presentation to the management.

Present the results to the management!

Presentation of results

Next, inform the management about the specific weaknesses of the company and suggested improvements, including the economic and ecological impact (worksheets 4 A and 4 B). In many projects it has proven very effective to present slides of the situation in the company and also positive examples at other companies.

Once you have obtained the management's approval for the planned measures, also secure support for implementation of the planned measures, i.e. the management must set a good example. Inform the management about who has been appointed waste officer in each area of the company.

Implement the specific company measures!

Now initiate the necessary work (ordering, installing and adapting waste collection points, creating information material, etc.) When the preparations have been completed and the newly labelled collection systems have arrived, combine installation of the new collection containers with a staff training scheme.

Implementation

In view of the fact that the company's waste management system should be supported by everyone, it is important to inform and motivate your colleagues with regard to correct separation of waste. One very helpful instrument is a company waste separation guide (see example 1, page 10).

When drawing up the guide, ensure that it contains the types of waste your colleagues deal with every day in their area of the company. Make the guide clear and attractive. For example, give each type of waste the key colour of the respective waste containers. This will make it much easier for your colleagues and will allow them to allocate waste to the correct category. Also, indicate a contact person in the guide to be contacted in case of uncertainty concerning separation of waste.

**Company waste
separation guide**

Don't forget to inform and instruct the company's own cleaners and cleaners from other firms! People in charge of repair and servicing and building maintenance are particularly important in terms of implementing the project!

Example 1: Waste Separation Guide

Waste paper	Glass	Hazardous waste	Bio waste
Paper, fax paper, carbon copy paper, envelopes incl. windows, flip chart paper, booklets, cardboard, paper packaging, newspapers, catalogues, brochures, etc.	Non-returnable bottles, jam jars, empty medicine bottles, other glass packaging	Batteries, used Texta 700, Tippex, stamp inks, stamp pads, cosmetics	Fruit and vegetable leftovers, coffee filters with grounds, food leftovers and chicken bones, wrapped in paper, cut flowers, potted plants, paper handkerchiefs, serviettes, tea-bags, etc.
No compound materials (e.g. Tetrapack), no plastic covers	No flat glass, mirror glass, crystal glass, wire glass (general waste)		
Metal	Fine fraction	General waste	
Aluminum and tin plate cans, bottle caps, aluminum caps, metal lids, aluminum film, aluminum lids of yoghurt pots, wire and other metal packaging, etc.	Packaging made of plastic, wood, compounds, and textile fibers, e.g. yoghurt pots, foils, light PET bottles, ceramic cosmetic and drink bottles, coffee packaging, detergent bottles, snack and pasta bags, coated meat and sausage wrapping paper, cigarette paper, drink boxes, etc.	Biros, felt pens, propelling pencils, ribbons, carbon paper, plastic folders, overhead transparencies, diskettes, rulers, light bulbs, cigarette ends and ashes, hygiene goods, sweepings, rubber, leather, etc.	

Example 1: Waste Separation Guide

3. OUR EXAMPLE – YOUR EXAMPLE: FROM THEORY TO PRACTICE

In order to simplify your analysis of the specific company waste management system, we have prepared an example of a fictitious brewery to show you what to do. But we will also present weaknesses and suggested improvements in the brewery example. You can use the empty worksheets to collect data on your own company, including specific weaknesses and suggested improvements.

Analysis of waste management by example of a brewery

Proceed as follows:

- Study the brewery example again
- Next, enter you company data in the empty worksheets, including weaknesses and suggested improvements

Worksheets

This Chapter contains the following worksheets:

- Worksheets 2 A - 2 B: "General waste management plan"
- Worksheets 3 A - 3 B: "Waste schedule"

Observe the procedure detailed in Chapter 2 when you begin to fill in the following worksheets with your specific company data, weaknesses and suggested improvements.

4. SUMMARY

4.1. How to prepare the results for presentation to the management

Presenting the results to the management

Are you surprised what possibilities exist to improve the waste management system? The preparations you and the environment task force have done are an important foundation for optimising the waste management system.

Now you need to win the management over for implementation and support of the planned measures. By example of the brewery we have drawn up presentation material based on the surveys.

If you like the presentation material and if you can make use of it, you will find empty forms in the appendix. Now try to draw up the material tuned to your company for presentation to the management in collaboration with the environment task force.

However, everyone involved must realise that the improved waste management system will need to be reviewed and updated on a regular basis.

Have fun!

In the brewery example we have prepared the following data for presentation:

- **“Waste logistics”**: Weaknesses - measures - impact (**worksheet 4 B**)

5. APPENDIX

Copy templates

Worksheet 2 A:	"General waste management plan"
Worksheet 2 B:	"Notes on the general waste management plan"
Worksheet 3 A-3 B:	"Waste schedule"
Worksheet 4 B:	"Waste logistics: weaknesses-measures - impact"

Worksheet 2 B Example
Notes on the general waste management plan

Areas	No. staff	Waste separation evaluation	Officers
A Delivery, storage	2	needs improving	Mr. Huber
B Malt shop	8	needs improving	Mr. Wallner
C Brew house section	3	needs improving	Mr. Meier
D Brew house	-	o.k.	Mr. Meier
E Fermenting and storage cellar	2	needs improving	Mr. Schauer
F Filtering cellar	-	o.k.	Mr. Schauer
G Bottling hall	6	needs improving	Mr. Flasche
H Dispatch, fleet	60	needs improving	Mr. Koch
I Petrol station	-	needs improving	Mr. Koch
K Lunch room	-	needs improving	Mr. Koch
L Administration	23	needs improving	Ms. Müller
M Canteen	2	needs improving	Ms. Lang
N Workshop, energy centre	4	needs improving	Ms. Heizer
O Waste collection point	-	needs improving	Mr. Vodisek

Notes:

Waste separation:

the existing system of waste separation is not adequate; biogenous waste (leftovers, flowers, etc.), metal packaging (except for aluminium cans), and fine fraction are not collected separately; discipline in terms of separating waste is poor, approx. 50% of industrial waste is recyclable waste; kieselguhr and labels are dumped.

Separation systems:

inadequate - provisional measures – unlabelled

Waste collection point:

sloppy, no one was responsible, the open general waste trough contains approx. 50% recyclable waste, there is a lack of collection containers for metal packaging, fine fraction and biogenous waste

Worksheet 3 A Example
Waste Schedule

Non-Hazardous Waste

Waste identifier	Item No. ¹	Volume waste p.a. [kg]	Collection/ treatment No. ²	Details of waste treatment in the company	Collection interval	Disposal costs p.a.
Draff	D	5,000,000	Farmers association	none	as required	Revenue 1.300
Malt rootlet	B	350,000	Farmers association	none	as required	Revenue 490
Malt dust	B,C	90,000	Farmers association	none	as required	Revenue 140
Grist	B	7,000	Farmers association	none	as required	-
Barley waste	B	220,000	Farmers association	none	as required	Revenue 440
Fodder yeast	E	30,000	Farmers association	none	as required	Revenue 60
Waste glass	G,H,L,M,N	92,000	Wegada	none	fortnightly	Revenue 32,20
Cardboard/paper	A,G,H,K-O	35,000	Wegada	none	fortnightly	-
Wooden pallets	G,H	24,000	Staff	none	as required	-
Plastic crates	A,G,H	18,000	Wegada	none	as required	-
Waste metal	N	8,000	Wegada	none	as required	-
Aluminium cans	G,A,H	1,500	Wegada	none	as required	Revenue 150
Plastic foils	A,G,H	1,500	Wegada	none	as required	-
Canteen leftovers	M	not ascertainable	Farmer	none	daily	-
Labels	G	50,000	Wegada	none	as required	125
Kieselguhr	F	45,000	Wegada	none	as required	112,50
Industrial waste	A-C,G-N	104,000	Wegada	none	weekly	260

¹ of the production site

² Indicate collection/treatment No. of disposer for hazardous waste and waste oil

Worksheet 3 B Example
Waste Schedule

Non-Hazardous Waste

Waste identifier	Item No. ¹	Volume waste p.a. [kg]	Collection/ treatment No. ²	Details of waste treatment in the company	Collection interval	Disposal costs p.a.
Waste separator contents	N	3,200	Wegada	none	as required	17.280
Workshop waste	N	200	Wegada	none	2xyear	3.900
Waste paint	N	50	Wegada 00322222	none	1xyear	800
Batteries unsorted	L, N	25	Umweltforum Batterien 22222222	none	1xyear	-
Fluorescent tubes	N	20	Wegada 00322222	none	1xyear	240
Cooling aggregates*	A	150	Wegada 00322222	none	as required	1.800
hazardous office waste	L	5	Wegada 00322222	none	1xyear	96

* : Key No. for cooling aggregates depends on the coolant used in the aggregate!

Waste Oils

Waste identifier	Item No. ¹	Volume waste p.a. [kg]	Collection/ treatment No. ²	Details of waste treatment in the company	Collection interval	Disposal costs p.a.
Waste oils	N	1,000	Wegada 00322222	none	as required	2.000

¹ of the production site

² Indicate collection/treatment No. of disposer for hazardous waste and waste oil

Worksheet 3 B Action Plan
Waste Schedule

Non-Hazardous Waste

Waste identifier	Item No. ¹	Volume waste p.a. [kg]	Collection/ treatment No. ²	Details of waste treatment in the company	Collection interval	Disposal costs p.a.

* : Key No. for cooling aggregates depends on the coolant used in the aggregate!

Waste Oils

Waste identifier	Item No. ¹	Volume waste p.a. [kg]	Collection/ treatment No. ²	Details of waste treatment in the company	Collection interval	Disposal costs p.a.

¹ of the production site

² Indicate collection/treatment No. of disposer for hazardous waste and waste oil

Worksheet 4 B Dossier 3 Example
Waste logistics: Weaknesses - Measures – Impact

What needs to be fulfilled/ improved?	Measures	Impact	Dead lines
Waste separation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Labels and kieselguhr will be supplied for farm composting. ▪ Waste separation systems will be purchased for fine fraction, metal packaging, and biogenous waste. ▪ Improvement of waste collecting discipline for all types of waste, specifically paper, cardboard, foils, hazardous waste by means of an improved waste logistics channel. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ This will save approx. x p.a. on disposal costs for labels and kieselguhr. ▪ This expanded and enhanced system of waste separation will entail an approx. 40 - 50 % reduction of industrial waste and will additionally save some ATS 130,000 p.a. 	<p>Jan 98</p> <p>Mar 98</p>
Waste separation systems	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Boxes will be removed as collection systems. ▪ New, labelled, user-friendly waste containers with the "waste key colours" (5l, 10l, 60l, 120l, 240l, 1.100l containers) will be purchased and existing collection systems appropriately adapted. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Fire hazard will be reduced. ▪ User-friendly systems of separation have a positive effect on staff discipline in terms of waste separation. 	<p>Mar 98</p>
Decentralise waste collection points	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Attractive decentralised waste collection points will be set up for the A-C and G-N areas. ▪ The wall panels will be painted in the company's green and information boards will be displayed. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Attractive waste collection points have a positive effect of staff discipline in terms of waste separation. ▪ Information and motivation of staff is increased. 	<p>Mar 98</p>
Design of the centralised waste collection point	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ The waste site will be tidied up and information boards will be displayed. ▪ The waste collection containers will be labelled and identified with the waste key colours. ▪ Additional container systems will be provided for fine fraction, biowaste and metal packaging. ▪ The general waste trough will be removed and replaced by a waste press container and 1.100l containers. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Promotes staff discipline in terms of waste separation. ▪ Staffs are motivated and informed. ▪ Improvement of quality of waste, reduction of industrial waste. 	<p>Mar 98</p>

Worksheet 4 B Dossier 3 Example
Waste logistics: Weaknesses - Measures – Impact

What needs to be fulfilled/ improved?	Measures	Impact	Dead lines
Waste officers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Waste officers have been installed for all areas (worksheet 2B) in order to ensure lasting implementation of the waste management system and inform staff in their areas. ▪ The names of the waste officers will be published in the company newspaper with a photograph and description of their responsibilities and tasks. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Waste officers in all areas ensure actual implementation of the company's waste management system. ▪ This facilitates and ensures a flow of information and training schemes at all levels. ▪ Motivated staff 	
Information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ A purchasing guide will be drawn up for the purchasing department so that it is always possible to review waste avoidance and substitution of materials and products that are seen as hazardous waste after use. ▪ Training of staff and cleaners when the new waste collection systems are installed. ▪ Further training to be specified. ▪ A company specific information sheet will be drawn up on waste separation. ▪ The management must set a good example in order to ensure credibility. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Informed and motivated staff. ▪ Everyone will contribute to implementing the company's waste management system. 	

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